

TEACH WITH ERASMUS+

ELTE Eötvös Loránd University
Department of Erasmus+ and
International Programmes

Teach with Erasmus+ Research Report

Erasmus+

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT

1.1.1 The changing context of higher education and internationalisation

Over the last decades, the rapid changes in the social and economic environment have been influencing higher education considerably. The growing emphasis on increasing migration, global integration, and other global processes (e.g. climate change, inequality) have **changed the landscape in which higher education institutions define their strategic goals and internationalizing activities.**

The **Leuven Communiqué** (signed by 46 countries of the Bologna Process in 2009) highlighted the importance of increasing the number of students (20% of the graduates by 2020) and staff participating in various mobility activities internationally. The Erasmus Impact Study (EIS) 2014 identified **staff mobility (including teachers) as a key factor** to be included as one of the **top priorities in the internationalisation strategies** of Higher Education Institutions (HEI) to reach the targets of the Leuven Communiqué.

Rooted in the Middle Ages, the **internationalisation in European higher education is not a new idea**: it has a long tradition and history. An extended understanding of internationalisation considers the phenomenon as “the intentional process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions and delivery of post-secondary education, in order to enhance the quality of education and research for all students and staff and to make a meaningful contribution to society” (*de Wit, Hunter, Howard, & Egron-Polak, 2015*). Institutions could have **many reasons for engaging in internationalisation**: increased international awareness of global issues by students, enhanced internationalisation of the curriculum, improved quality of teaching and learning, strengthened institutional research and knowledge production capacity, enhanced profile for the institution, opportunity to benchmark institutional performance within the context of international good practice, enhanced institutional cooperation and capacity building, increased international networking by faculty and researchers and increased/diversified revenue generation (*Seeber, Cattaneo, Huisman, & Paleari, 2016*).

In Europe, international higher education (student, staff, and teaching) **mobility is the most visible facet of higher education internationalisation**. In Europe, the main driver for higher education mobility is the Erasmus+ programme. In 2017, which was the 30th anniversary year of the programme, more than 312 300 student and 62 500 staff mobilities were supported.

It is undeniable that **internationalisation can lead to a diverse set of desirable outcomes** and impacts regarding the operation of higher education institutions and academics’ professional development, but it must be noted that universities are often considering such indicators like proportions of international staff, number of international students, research papers published with a co-author from another country etc., which limits our understanding of the possible supporting and hindering factors behind internationalisation.

1.1.2 Research on teaching mobility

While there are many aspects of internationalisation, **this report only focuses on academics' mobility and in particular, teaching mobility**. Generally, **staff mobility is given less focus in research regarding the internationalisation of higher education** and also, institutional strategies seem to be rarely systematic in promoting this opportunity (*de Wit et al.*, 2015), and it is rarely recognised towards career progression (*Racké*, 2013). Previous research uncovered that **a strategic approach to academic mobility has clear advantages for research, teaching and professional development** (*Colucci, Ferencz, Gaebel & Wächter*, 2014; *Svetlik & Braček Lalić*, 2016). The strategic role of academic mobility was reassured by Postiglione and Altbach (2013) as well. Teaching mobility can also play an important role in joint programmes, and through those, in the internationalisation at home agenda of institutions (*Erdei et al.*, 2018).

Despite its strategic importance and possible impacts, **outcomes assessment of staff mobility strongly focuses on input and output indicators and lacking important contextual and process elements** (*Deardoff & van Gaalen*, 2012; *Chang & Lin*, 2018). Therefore, a more rigorous and complex measurement regarding the topic is needed, e.g. from a **quality assurance perspective** (*Voroshilova*, 2015; *Hauptman Komotar*, 2018), taking into consideration **personality factors** (*Dewey & Duff*, 2009; *Li & Tu*, 2016) and the **pedagogical dimension** as well (*Wihlborg*, 2009).

1.1.3 The Teach with Erasmus+ project

The **Teach with Erasmus+ project (TWE+)**, as a logical continuation and extension of the staffmobility.eu website of the IMOTION project aims to create an online *'Marketplace'* for teaching staff in order to **facilitate, encourage, and promote teachers' mobility across Europe**.

In order to help to fulfil this aim, the project has the objective to **identify and define quality teaching mobility**. This particular Intellectual Output (IO1) consists of exploratory research on quality aspects of teaching mobility that is followed by the development of the actual **"Quality & Impact Tool for Teaching Mobility Assessment" (QITMA)** and is one of the four main pillars of the TWE+ project.

The project is realised by a consortium consisting of: **ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Institut polytechnique UniLaSalle, University of Alcalá, UNICA and European University Foundation**. The results of the project are disseminated through the <https://teachwitherasmus.eu/> website.

1.2 THE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

The research involved a mixed-methods strategy, combining qualitative and quantitative tools to have a broader understanding of the research questions. A preliminary, qualitative-focused research was applied in order to map the basic domains that could be involved in a large scale survey:

- 33 semi-structured interview conducted by members of the consortium from various countries

- 1 focus-group where various stakeholders shared their experiences through a customer journey mapping process

A large, international survey-based quantitative research were employed based on the results of the interviews distributed by the networks of the consortium members. The main aim was to reach at least 500 participants from different Erasmus+ Programme Country in order to be able to generate meaningful groupings and comparisons during the data analysis. Signaling the significance of the topic, at the end of the data gathering we have managed to surpass our initial goal regarding the number of participants (N=745, which will be detailed later).

The survey comprises of four blocks, one of which is for only those who have participated in teaching mobility before. Therefore, the research encompasses the experiences of those who have not participated in teaching mobility before in the hope of discovering the main barriers of abstaining as well.

The general structure of the questionnaire makes it possible to gather relevant organisational contextual data, data regarding personal aspects and factors related to a concrete mobility experience. A unique part of the survey is the third block, where we ask participants to think about a concrete mobility experience they had and the survey guides them to better focus on that memory with few introductory questions (e.g. when and where was the mobility). This would allow us to gather more specific data, tied to a real experience instead of a general approach.

In the survey, we implemented several standardized scales that have been used in previous research which would allow us an international and intersectoral comparison. The following scales are used:

- **International orientation and strategy of the institution:** the items are taken from a dimension of the HEInnovate tool
- **Personality factors:** Based on the interviews Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (*Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004*), ambiguity tolerance (*Herman et al., 2010*) and self-efficacy (*Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995*) were used.

The survey was followed-up by several post-interview to help us better understand the results that our analysis provided.

This research project will allow us to explore the following broad research questions and aims which will be examined via exploratory and multivariate statistical procedures:

- 1) What are the main differences between higher education systems, different types of institutions and different individuals regarding their attitudes and experiences towards teaching mobility?
- 2) What are the main outcomes and impacts of teaching mobility?
- 3) What are the main factors that could restrain individuals from engaging in teaching mobility?
- 4) What are the main factors that influence individuals' willingness to participate in and satisfaction with teaching mobility?
- 5) What are the main factors that influence the possible outcomes of teaching mobility?

The research project is approved by the Research Ethics Board of the Faculty of Education and Psychology of Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE). The research is planned and executed by

concerning general standards for social sciences and humanities research (regarding human participation) and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

1.3 MAIN RESULTS AND FINDINGS OF THE RESEARCH

1.3.1 The sample

After data-cleaning, the final database contained responses from **745 academics from European HEIs**. Academics in the sample are mainly **from state or public HEIs (94,1%)**. Considering general demographic variables, 42,2% of the respondents are male, while 57,8% are female. Respondents are **fairly balanced regarding disciplinary orientation**. Most of the participants are from the field of social sciences (34,9%) and humanities (21,9%), while engineering disciplines are represented by 18,2% of the sample. The sample contains academics that have **already participated in teaching mobility (69%)** and those **who haven't participated yet (31%)** which is an important dimension to compare.

Although our study is not based on a representative sample, for the sake of the **explorative nature** of this research we can say that we have a fairly balanced sample which could provide valuable insights for developing a quality tool for teaching mobility.

1.3.2 Characteristics of reported teaching mobilities

The following questions (background information on the mobility experience, mobility factors, satisfaction with the experience and results and feedback sections) were only asked from those who have already participated in teaching mobility. The survey explicitly asked respondents to think about a certain teaching mobility experience and answer the questions in light of that specific experience. With this solution, the researchers tried to influence respondents in a way that they focus on a specific experience rather than generalities. Most of the sample consists of academics who have already been on teaching mobility (69%, N=455). **Most of the teaching mobilities reported in our survey were quite recent, 65,9% of them were realized in 2018 and 2019**. The most frequent countries to visit are Spain, Poland, France, Germany and Portugal (covering 36,7% of valid responses).

Participating in Erasmus+ teaching mobility programmes is related to some personal characteristics. A test of independence on this data shows that there are significant associations: **those who have participated in Erasmus+ programmes are more likely to have higher academic rank, more work experience and are from the older age groups**.

Institutional factors, such as the size or type of higher education institute are not related to participation, however, there are **significant associations with organisational support and strategic focus** on internationalization or with **the presence of mobility as expectation**.

1.3.3 Personality factors influencing teaching mobility

The Erasmus Impact Study used 6 memo© factors: curiosity, serenity, confidence, tolerance for ambiguity, decisiveness, vigour. In relation to these factors, we chose to integrate three measures:

- **tolerance for ambiguity scale** (*Herman et al, 2010*)

- **work-engagement** as measured in vigour, dedication and absorption using the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale 9 items version (*Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004*)
- general **self-efficacy** scale (*Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995*)

Regarding descriptive results, it is not necessary to go into details analysing these numbers. We can acknowledge that regarding work engagement scale, our sample presents a rather high average, where absorption and dedication plays a more important role than vigour. On the other hand, measured personality factors like self-efficacy and tolerance of ambiguity also came up quite high. These variables will be examined in relations of different target groups.

As for personal attitudes there are several significant correlations with hindering factors. It is worth to highlight, that **intercultural difficulties** (such as variant education system, students' expectations or research culture of the host institutions) are **only connected to personal attitudes**, while **socio-demographic or organisational factors are independent of it**. **Self-efficacy, dedication and absorption are all significantly associated with intercultural difficulties**. **The more positive attitude participants have, the fewer difficulties they face** regarding different attitudes in the host country.

1.3.4 The influence of strategic approach to and organizational support of internationalisation on teaching mobility

Respondents feel that their organisation supports teaching mobility as **academics have the opportunity to organise their classes in a way that they could go on a teaching mobility (65,3%** of respondents stated that this is rather true in their university), and they **feel supported in their endeavours (63,9%** showed positive orientation towards this statement). Besides the reported positive atmosphere regarding support of internationalisation, it seems **when substitutions come into question, respondents are less likely to report positive attitudes (39,8%** of respondents stated that if he/she would miss a class at home due to being on teaching mobility, the organisation wouldn't provide a substitution). Furthermore, it seems that teaching mobility is **not well-recognized in academics' career development (23,9%** of respondents were not agreeing to the statement that teaching mobility is a recognized activity in their organisation). **Internationalisation became an integral part of HEIs operation, 76%** of respondents stated that internationalisation is an important part of the institution's strategy and **68%** perceived that **they have some kind of incentive of support mechanisms in place for this field**. Although the **recruitment of international staff members is not that prevalent (23,9%** disagrees with the statement that their organisation is trying to attract academics and staff member with international orientation).

Organisational support on internationalization also affects how respondents consider some of the factors. Difference between institutes with low support comparing to high supporters is statistically proven with the following factors: lack of time and financial support, lack of competence and motivation and lack of benefits. While facing the **difficulties of lack of time, support and benefits appear in organisations with low support**, lack of motivation reflects the opposite tendency: **those who teach in highly supportive institutions, facing less (or none) difficulties with lack of competence or motivation.**

1.3.5 Factors that hinder participation in teaching mobility

The **most important hindering factors** reported by participants are considering the **administrative and organization tasks** regarding mobility. 30,55% of respondents stated that it is a **great inconvenience to organise and realise teaching mobility**, while 28,32% fear that the **budget won't be enough to cover their expenses**, 26,4% has **issues with solving their substitution at their home university for the duration of the mobility**. In order to have a clearer picture regarding hindering factors, we employed data reduction methods (exploratory factor analysis) to uncover the latent structure between variables describing hindering factors. 5 factors were extracted explaining 61,65% of the total variance: lack of time and financial support, lack of connections and reputation or communication issues, lack of competence and motivation, intercultural difficulties, no benefits.

Participating in Erasmus+ affects how respondents see hindering factors regarding teaching mobility, however, intercultural issues (such as variant education system, student expectations and research attitudes in the host country) and the lack of competence or motivation are at the same level in both groups. Nevertheless, **dealing with lack of time, connections or benefits when talking about teaching mobility programmes tends to disappear among those, who have already tried themselves abroad.**

Where respondents have no **information about teaching mobility programmes, the lack of time, financial support and the lack of benefits are significantly higher**, showing the importance of formal dissemination when someone participated in teaching mobility program. However, organizing **formal events** after a colleague participated in a particular teaching mobility program **raises the degree of concern about the lack of competence and motivation**.

1.3.6 Factors that motivate academics to participate in teaching mobilities

Based on the results of the preliminary interviews and focus group, we identified 15 items that could describe the possible range of motivations. The data tells us, that academics who have participated in teaching mobility were **mainly motivated** by their inner curiosity to **learn new educational practices** (84,4% felt that this was very important motivation for them), and to **learn about the research projects of the host institution** (81,3% found it very important). On the other side, it seems that **expectations or encouragement from the organisation or the leadership is simply not that important** (55,6% and 53,1% stated that these factors were not important in their decision), also which is quite contradictory to our expectations, **recommendations from colleagues proved to be a weak factor as well** (45,6% stated that this was not important). We used data reduction techniques here as well for us to be able to present a more focused analysis of the different groups regarding their motivation. The 4 principal components extracted explained 70,54% of the total variance: learning (languages, pedagogical methods), getting to know new places and cultures, research opportunities, expectation and urge.

The motivation of learning is connected to age, title and vigour, and it is also affected by discipline and organisational support on mobility programmes. Getting to know new cultures only relates to vigour and tolerance for ambiguity, while research opportunity is associated with both personal attitudes and disciplines. Self-efficacy and absorption lead to higher motivation of research opportunities, as well as being a lecturer in the field of natural sciences, engineering or agriculture and veterinary. Expectation and urge are higher among women, among those who scored higher in vigour and dedication on work, and among those who are more intolerant for ambiguity. It is also connected to the organisational profile, where high supportive institutions lead to a higher score for urge and expectation as a motivational factor. Urge and expectation is also higher among short-termed and repeated mobility, suggesting that younger participants rather have internal motivation (such as learning, getting to know new places, seizing research opportunity), while older respondents, who have participated in teaching mobility programmes earlier tend to have external motivation which is expectation or urge.

1.3.7 Satisfaction with teaching mobility

It seems that those who have participated in teaching mobilities reported a **rather high satisfaction regarding different elements** of the programme. Respondents were **most satisfied with the help they received from the host institution** organising the mobility (82,91% were rather satisfied with this element), and with **the time frame of the mobility** (81,03% were rather satisfied). Academics were **least satisfied with the administrative process** (only 66,82% reported that they are rather satisfied) and the **amount of financial support** (only 66,44% reported that they are rather satisfied).

Besides the specific elements, the survey also measured **respondents' general satisfaction with their teaching mobility experience using a Net Promoter Score (NPS) approach**. Respondents who gave a score of 0-6 are grouped as “Detractors”, those who gave 7 or 8 are grouped as “Passive” and those, who scored 9 or 10 are belong to the “Promoter” category. The NPS is calculated by subtracting the percentage of detractors from the percentage of promoters. Considering the **overall satisfaction** of respondents with their teaching mobility experience, it seems that they **rated it as excellent**, as it is evident from the reported NPS values (56 and 63,4 for overall satisfaction and return-intent respectively). The **intention to repeat the mobility** (with the same conditions) could **signal a strong commitment towards the experience and in return, a strong indicator for satisfaction**.

Respondents' **mobility intention are correlated with self-efficacy and each component of work engagement**, while **none of the socio-demographic factors affects it significantly**. On the other hand, organizational factors are also related to mobility intention: in **those institutions where mobility is highly supported, respondents' intention to participate in mobility programmes are significantly higher**.

Motivation and hindering factors also connect to **mobility intention**, where **learning and getting to know new places show positive relationship** (meaning that higher motivation on these components results in higher mobility intention) while hindering factors show negative association: the **more concerns respondents have, the lower his mobility intention is**. There is a significant and strong correlation between the satisfaction with mobility programme and return intent: **higher the satisfaction, greater the return intent is**. Except for tolerance of ambiguity, both self-efficacy and elements of work engagement (vigour, dedication and absorption) are in a positive association, meaning that **more positive attitude comes with higher satisfaction with mobility programme, and higher return intent, as well**.

Useful **feedback from students, self-efficacy and hindering factor of no benefits explains 22% of satisfaction**, where feedback and self-efficacy contribute positively and the lack of benefits¹ affects satisfaction negatively.

Significant **positive connection between return intent and learning motivation**, while the **lack of benefits, time and financial support negatively affects it**.

1.3.8 Possible contributions and perceived results of teaching mobility

In the survey, we used items describing **potential results** that we identified through the preliminary interviews and focus group. Initially, we clustered results around broader topics: **education** (8 items, eg. better teaching competence, new pedagogical methods), **research** (9 items, eg. opportunity to present empirical results at a conference, joining to a research team), **professional development** (14 items, eg. networking, development of interpersonal competencies) and **organisational results** (7 items, eg. greater intense of student mobility and cooperation with host institute).

The most important results reported by academics are the **expansion of their professional network (71,2%** rated this as a direct result of their mobility), **getting to know the culture, the educational system and the operation of higher education institutions in a foreign country (65,6%** stated that it was a direct result of their mobility), and **getting to know the work-culture of another organisation (64,3%** stated that it was a direct result of their mobility). On the other hand, it seems that teaching mobility **rarely contributes to introducing new joint degree programmes (79,1%** reported that this hasn't happened), **nor new courses/modules (65,8%** reported that this hasn't happened). Overall, respondents rated items regarding **professional development higher** than those items that are dealing with other possible results.

These types of **results may be predicted by different factors**, which was examined by regression models. Numbers show that there **are some common factors** that affect each kind of results, such as **feedback from students, previous experience and the motivation of research opportunities** – three of the predictive factors from the derived results variable emerged in each of the segmented prediction models, as well. Results on the side of **education** can be predicted by **the level of learning motivation and organizational expectation**, while results connected to **research** are only affected by **organizational strategy on internationalization** (above the common factors). **Organizational results** are higher with **higher concerns about lack of competence and motivation, higher expectation and higher self-efficacy**. **Professional development** has the most significant connection, it is growing with each component of **motivation plus with higher concerns about lack of competence**. Each connection is significant and positive, meaning that higher predictive factors grow the level of results in each component.

¹ Negative scale for hindering factors means less concern about the particular factor, therefore negative affect means that less concern will result in higher satisfaction.

1.4 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In summary, **respondents differ within the categories of participants and non-participants** in academic rank, age and work experience:

- seizing the opportunity of gathering teaching experience abroad with Erasmus+ is more favoured among non-starter professors, according to the sample
- the organisational profile also determines participation: institutions where strategic focus and support on internationalization is higher, and where they provide more information about teaching mobility programmes, have a higher ratio of Erasmus+ participants.

According to **hindering factors**, both organisational attitudes, information flow and mobility as expectation seems to be affected by disciplines, which then affects the degree of particular hindering factors:

- fields where organisational support on mobility programmes are high result in fewer concerns about the lack of time, financial support and benefits while raising the scores for lack of competence and motivation.

Personal characteristics were only connected to lack of connections, reputation or communication issues from hindering factors:

- the association may be tracked back to participating in Erasmus + programmes: sociodemographic factors (except for gender) are significantly related to participation

in Erasmus+ teaching mobility programme, which then affects how respondents consider lack of connections, reputation or communication issues. With higher position, longer work experience and older age respondents face fewer difficulties according to this factor

- international issues are correlated to personal attitudes, where higher scores correlate to fewer concerns of international issues.

Different elements of motivation depend on various factors, suggesting that younger participants rather have the internal motivation (such as learning, getting to know new places, seizing research opportunity), while older and more experienced respondents, who have participated in teaching mobility programmes earlier tend to have external motivation which is expectation or urge:

- learning is connected to age, title and vigour work as personal factors, and it is also affected by discipline and organisational support on mobility programmes: higher motivation appears in the field of health - and medical sciences
- getting to know new cultures only relates to vigour work engagement and tolerance for ambiguity
- self-efficacy and absorption leads to higher motivation of research opportunities, as well as being a lecturer in the field of natural sciences, engineering or agriculture and veterinary
- expectation and urge are higher among women, among those who scored higher in vigour and dedication on work, and among those who are more intolerant for ambiguity. It is also connected to the organisational profile, where high supportive institutions lead to a higher score, and it is also higher among short-termed programmes and repeated mobility.

Mobility intention is connected to motivation and hindering factors and some of the personal attitudes and organizational factors:

- highly supportive organization shows a higher intention
- mobility intention is higher among regional studies compared to foreign language or nationally embedded disciplines
- higher motivation results in higher mobility intention while hindering factors reduce the level of mobility intention
- higher self-efficacy and work engagement comes with higher mobility intention.

Overall satisfaction with teaching mobility programme and return intent are both related to personal attitudes and organisational profile, but they are independent of sociodemographic factors and discipline.

- participants are most satisfied with the help from the host country and with time-frame of the programme, while financial support and administration are the least satisfying

- motivational factors also correlate to some of the elements of teaching mobility programmes, showing that higher motivation comes with higher satisfaction
- return intent can be enhanced by greater learning motivation and fewer concerns about benefits, time and financial support, according to a predictive model
- overall satisfaction is affected by the amount of feedback from students, self-efficacy and lack of benefits.

Results experienced by participants depend on personal characteristics, such as gender and age, and also some personal attitudes (self-efficacy, work engagement and tolerance for ambiguity):

- women reported more professional development than men
- organization results ended up higher among younger respondents
- higher scores on personal attitudes show more experience, except for tolerance of ambiguity which comes with a negative correlation
- organisational support on teaching programmes also affects results, higher support means considering more results
- level of motivation and satisfaction connects to results as well, on a positive way
- according to a predictive model, higher motivation in expectation or research opportunities will lead to a greater amount of results of teaching mobility programmes.

2 INTRODUCTION

The Leuven Communiqué (signed by 46 countries of the Bologna Process in 2009) highlighted the importance of increasing the number of students (20% of the graduates by 2020) and staff participating in various mobility activities internationally. The Erasmus Impact Study (EIS) 2014 identified staff mobility (including teachers) as a key factor to be included as one of the top priorities in the internationalisation strategies of Higher Education Institutions (HEI) to reach the targets of the Leuven Communiqué.

Based on the results of the EIS, several research efforts have been carried out to analyse the different characteristics of higher education teachers' mobility. These studies discovered several reasons and obstacles that prevent staff from making full use of this opportunity which is primarily linked to suboptimal strategy, misaligned management, poor promotion/dissemination and issues with recognition from the perspectives of academic career. These obstacles are particularly pertinent for junior researchers, which often lack personal networks abroad.

The **Teach with Erasmus+ project (TWE+)**, as a **logical continuation and extension of the staffmobility.eu website of the IMOTION project** aims to create an online *'Marketplace'* for teaching staff in order to **facilitate, encourage, and promote teachers' mobility across Europe**. The project aims to **enable greater access to teaching mobility and to compile innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogical tools** all over Europe. This would be an unprecedented and crucial innovation for the European Higher Education Area, which would address some of the most pressing concerns and obstacles to academic mobility in the EU.

In order to help to fulfil this aim, the project has the objective to **identify and define quality teaching mobility**. This particular Intellectual Output (IO1) consists of exploratory research on quality aspects of teaching mobility that is followed by the development of the actual **"Quality & Impact Tool for Teaching Mobility Assessment" (QITMA)** and is one of the four main pillars of the TWE+ project. In the premises of this research, an exploratory survey on elements connected to teaching mobility needs to be undertaken. This research will feed into the development of the actual tool.

The primary aim of the research is to develop and validate the main dimensions and indicators for the quality measurement tool. The development process is formed by a literature review and qualitative data gathering from consortium members via interviews. A **survey instrument** has been developed based on the interviews containing the most important indicators, possible benefits and hindering factors of realising quality teaching mobility. Psychometric properties of the instrument will be assessed, and multivariate statistical analysis will be carried out in order to finalise the tool. The results of the research will make it possible **to create a concise, understandable measurement tool for public use**. The tool will help HEIs or organisations **receive a tangible, up-to-date, evidence-based and objective picture about the current quality of teaching mobility** at their institution.

3 THEORETICAL UNDERPINNINGS OF THE RESEARCH

3.1 QUALITY AGENDA IN HIGHER EDUCATION

The quality of higher education has become a focus area in recent decades. Quality has always been part of the academic life, in the forms of informal peer reviews and self-regulation. In the last decades, several changes have contributed to the emergence of the quality movement. One factor that has led to greater attention to quality assurance is massification (increasing number of students and heterogeneity of student body) that has caused fundamental structural changes in higher education and rising budgetary pressures on both higher education institutions and national governments. The other reason is the introduction of New Public Management in higher education that – with its focus on leadership, efficiency, and effectiveness – has been a contributor to a greater focus on the quality of higher education (Matei & Iwinski, 2016). The adoption of quality management ideas has been superficial in some cases and diluted by the exercise of academic freedom.

The impact of transnational or international policies such as the Bologna Process or European integration has also significantly influenced developments in the area of quality assurance. Due to the Bologna Process, especially the recognition of degrees and study periods, the quality of higher education has been valued on the international, national and institutional levels. The Bologna countries continuously develop their higher education systems strengthening their quality assurance mechanisms. As a result of recent developments, the focus of teaching and learning has shifted from the process to the student, which means the quality systems have paid more attention to what students are learning and how to provide them with more learning opportunities.

Quality is a much-debated term, especially in terms of higher education. There are many approaches and a wide variety of interpretations applied in the large body of scientific literature (Schindler, Puls-Elvidge, Welzant, & Crawford, 2015). Quality in higher education simply means the educational process that ensures students achieve their goals. However, the picture of defining quality is more complex. Many authors highlight that the definition of quality in higher education is difficult to grasp, and there are more strategies to define the term. Most definition attempts to emphasize the importance of the local/institutional. Mishra (2007) argues that around the various concepts there are few central ideas such as quality defined as culture, as a process, as relative and absolute terms. According to Matei & Iwinski (2016), quality has defined differently in various contexts. Harvey and Green (1993, cited by Matei & Iwinski, 2016) proposed five “ways of thinking about quality”, rather than definitions, they offer a framework for thinking about the topic. The five ways of thinking are the following: quality as exceptional/excellence, as perfection or consistency, as fitness for purpose, as the value of money and as transformation. Another important challenge regarding the definition of quality, that it is an “elusive term” and its definition depends on the different views of stakeholders in higher education (Schindler *et al.*, 2015).

In summary, there is no single way to define quality there are more classifications that are applied in the context of higher education. The definition should be developed and adapted to the local, institutional context, and in an institution, the various stakeholders should create a common understanding of quality.

However, it is an important question, how quality can be assessed and assured in higher education. The goal of quality assurance is to maintain and enhance the quality of educational services and products. Quality assurance is the responsibility of every actor in an institution of higher education, from the top management to the students. Quality assurance is a continuous process that has two main purposes, traditional definitions of quality assurance focus on accountability and improvement (*Matei & Iwinski, 2016*).

Many authors emphasize that quality assurance is a set of processes, policies, and actions achieved externally by quality assurance agencies and accreditation bodies or internally within the institutions (*Schindler, Puls-Elvidge, Welzant, & Crawford, 2015*). Internal quality management is a crucial element in the everyday life of higher education. The growing emphasis of internal quality management is reflected by the ever-increasing number of policy documents and handbooks that provide toolkits for developing internal procedures (IQM-HE, 2016). In national higher education systems, which are based on the principles of university autonomy, it is typically the institutions themselves that are seen as key agents and experts responsible for assuring the quality of their processes. There are different ways of internal quality assurance, for instance, self-evaluation, peer review techniques, and analysis of various indicators and data, surveys for institutional actors, and testing the knowledge or competences of students or teachers (*Mishra, 2007*).

The main form of external quality assurance is accreditation that has been systematically spread in Europe due to the Bologna process. As a result of the Bologna implementation, the organizational system of external quality assurance has been developing over the past two decades. European cooperation in the field of quality assurance is one of the most important Bologna tools. The European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA) initiated and developed the European Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG). The document was adopted by ministers in 2005 at the Ministerial Conference in Bergen (*EHEA, 2019*). The ESG defines standards for internal and external quality assurance, and the following principles: institutions have primary responsibility for the quality of their provision and its assurance; the quality of academic programmes needs to be developed and improved for student and other beneficiaries of higher education, transparency in quality assurance processes, the encouragement of a culture of quality, higher education institutions should demonstrate their accountability, and their quality internationally and nationally, quality assurance takes into account the needs and expectations of students, all other stakeholders, and society (*ESG, 2015*). The ESG has become the main guideline in the development of internal and external quality assurance processes in the higher education system.

3.2 INTERNATIONALISATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION

Over the last decades, the rapid changes in the social and economic environment have been influencing higher education considerably. The impact of global trends in recent decades (such as demographic changes, changes in social and economic structure and technological developments) on higher education is undeniable; they have had a decisive influence on trends in education and training.

The growing emphasis on increasing migration, global integration, and other global processes (e.g. climate change, inequality) have changed the landscape in which higher education institutions define their strategic goals and internationalizing activities. In recent decades, the importance of building the knowledge economy has led to a demand for a highly skilled workforce and the RDI (research-development-innovation) sector has strengthened at local, regional and global levels. These developments have increased the role and importance of quality education and training for the labour market. This also prompted higher education institutions to put more emphasis on developing intercultural competence for both students and academic staff. Therefore, it is not surprising that in the last few decades – besides quality -, internationalisation has become one of the most significant trends in European higher education. Higher education institutions are complex organizations that have significantly influenced by the wider social and economic environment, and this is undoubtedly reflected in their core functions of teaching and learning, research and services.

Rooted in the Middle Ages, the internationalisation in European higher education is not a new idea: it has a long tradition and history. Since the establishment of universities, the international dimension of institutions has been determinative in different forms. Since the 1980s, internationalisation has stepped into a new phase as evidenced by the following trends: the dramatic increase of international (student, staff, and teaching) mobility, the strengthening of the regional approach in institutional collaborations, and the European integration in the field of education and training. Over the last two decades, internationalisation of higher education has shifted from marginal to core trend in higher education.

Internationalisation became a strategic priority in higher education development, especially in the European Union, as a means of aligning learning outcomes with labour market needs and to enhance innovation capacity. The loose policy mechanism of the Bologna Process is an important drive for the internationalisation agenda, but it is an important task to assess its results, especially in the light of recent international challenges like Brexit, increased migration, the debate on English vs. local language etc. These challenges bring about the need to rethink our standpoint regarding internationalisation and consider it from a value-based approach in order to further the goals of developing global citizenship and intercultural understanding (*Wilhborg & Robson, 2017; Teichler, 2009*). An extended understanding of internationalisation considers the phenomenon as “the intentional process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions and delivery of post-secondary education, in order to enhance the quality of education and research for all students and staff and to make a meaningful contribution to society” (*de Wit, Hunter, Howard, & Egron-Polak, 2015*).

The internationalising process brought an increased role of knowledge transfer in the higher education system, a growing activity of international mobility and the establishment of international cooperation in the field of higher education and research. Regionalisation is a key form of internationalisation, in Europe, the cooperation between higher education institutions or student mobility within a specific region became crucial. The term Europeanisation is applied primarily to examine the intra-European cooperation (e.g. the Erasmus programme) and the impact of the Bologna Process. Europeanisation is viewed as a form of internationalisation, and it is understood as institutionalisation of different forms of rules developed in a process that involves supranational or intergovernmental bodies (e.g. EU, Bologna process). The rationales and incentives for internationalisation are varied, and influenced by different stakeholders: economic, social, cultural and academic rationales are deployed to support the internationalising processes. Emphasizing the academic rationale, the international dimension of higher education is inevitable: the international approach leads to more interdisciplinary research cooperation, which has an impact on teaching and learning at higher education as well.

While the idea of internationalisation has been around since the dawn of universities, it is now influenced by globalisation and the raising of the knowledge society which gave a new breadth and depth to the concept. Internationalisation is often mentioned beside increasing reputation (rankings), visibility and competitiveness, the competition for talent and the focus on employability and social mobility (*de Wit et al.*, 2015). Institutions could have many reasons for engaging in internationalisation: increased international awareness of global issues by students, enhanced internationalisation of the curriculum, improved quality of teaching and learning, strengthened institutional research and knowledge production capacity, enhanced profile for the institution, opportunity to benchmark institutional performance within the context of international good practice, enhanced institutional cooperation and capacity building, increased international networking by faculty and researchers and increased/diversified revenue generation (*Seeber, Cattaneo, Huisman, & Paleari*, 2016).

Internationalisation represents an ongoing debate and is frequently problematized. In the last decades, there have been several significant concerns about the direction of internationalisation. These critiques are varied, some experts highlight the challenges of uncoordinated, fragmented institutional-level practices, and they promote strategic, coordinated and systematic policies and practices at the institutional level.

Due to the above-mentioned developments, the role of academic staff has also changed. In our days, academics are increasingly required to be open, speak multiple foreign languages, and participate in international research and development projects. Therefore, academic staff members need to follow recent trends and demands of the labour market.

3.3 POLICY CONTEXT OF HIGHER EDUCATION

The economic and social changes have been expressed in the Bologna process. Over the last twenty years, European higher education, at the international, national and institutional level, has been fundamentally transformed by the Bologna Process. The creation of the European

Higher Education Area (EHEA) can be seen both as a primary tool for the European integration process and as the main driver for the internationalisation process of higher education. Since the Bologna Declaration in 1999, there has been significant policy interest to adopt the Bologna model in the European higher education scheme.

Initially, the Bologna Process served primarily economic purposes, which was reflected in the main objectives declared in the Bologna Declaration. At the same time, the social and cultural role of higher education needed to be redefined, while strengthening the competitiveness of European higher education. The main elements of the Bologna model are the introduction of a common qualification framework (2, and since 2003, the 3-cycle system), the implementation of the European Credit Transfer System, the strengthening of European coordination in the field of quality management and the student-centred teaching and learning principles. Since its inception, spatial mobility has been a key element in the Bologna Process. The adaptation of the Bologna model has brought new challenges for institutions of higher education.

Over the past decades, the Bologna Process has become decisive cooperation, mainly at European level, which formulated outside the institutional framework of the European Union, but in close cooperation with EU policies. The establishment of the EHEA has become a central element of higher education in the European Union in recent decades, and many of the EU policy objectives and activities are in line with the implementation of the Bologna Process. The number of Bologna countries is 48 since 2015 - however, this group of countries goes beyond Europe, and more Asian countries are becoming members of the process.

The role of higher education in the process of European integration has evolved. Although the first signs of integration efforts were indicated in the field of education and training, higher education policy efforts started during the late eighties. Then, student mobility in Europe gained attention with the launch of various mobility programmes. A major step in the field of higher education mobility was the launch of the Erasmus programme in 1987, the countries of the former Eastern block joined the programme during the mid-nineties. The programme aimed to have 10% of higher education students pursuing their studies in another European country for some time.

In 2000, the Lisbon Strategy and later, the EU2020 Strategy provided fundamental changes in goal setting related to education and training in the European Union. According to the Lisbon Strategy, in Europe, it is essential to build a knowledge-based economy to respond to the challenges of globalization effectively. This approach particularly values the role of education and training. The goals of the Europe 2020 (a strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth) are not focusing exclusively on leading the European Union out of the economic and social crisis, but on creating incentives for growth. The strategy sets out five headline targets in a number of areas, such as education, training and employment. The importance of mobility is highlighted in this process. According to the strategy, promoting student mobility and teaching mobility contribute to enhancing the quality and international attractiveness of Europe's higher education institutions.

By the end of the 1990s, EU-financed programmes had become a fundamental basis for higher education mobility. Between 2014 and 2020, Erasmus+ programme support actions in the fields of education and training, youth and sport, with a budget of EUR 16.45 billion. The programme provides over 4 million persons with the opportunity to gain competences and have a personal, socio-educational and professional development through studies, training, work experience or volunteering abroad worldwide. The programme supports the mobility of individuals, and organizations to build cooperation for innovation and good practices and also supports policy reform. The programme provides mobility opportunities for students, and staff members of higher education in the following action types: KA103 - Higher education students and staff mobility within programme countries, and KA107 - Higher education students and staff mobility between programme and partner countries.

3.4 HIGHER EDUCATION MOBILITY

In Europe, international higher education (student, staff, and teaching) mobility is the most visible facet of higher education internationalisation. Since the 1990s, mobility tendencies have been increasing, and more countries have been involved in the process.

Since its inception, higher education mobility has been a central element in the Bologna Process. By implementing the Bologna model, institutions of higher education were encouraged to develop their activities for enhancing student and staff mobility. Overall, student mobility in Europe has been increasing over the last decades. In the context of the Bologna Process, higher education mobility is seen as a generally positive process, a success story. In the OECD countries, the trends of international student mobility have increased significantly: in 2017 overall 5.3 million students pursue their higher education studies abroad. The increase in the rate of higher education mobility will be expected to continue, but the intensity and forms of mobility are changing.

In Europe, the main driver for higher education mobility is the Erasmus+ programme. In 2017, which was the 30th anniversary year of the programme, more than 312 300 student and 62 500 staff mobilities were supported. Showing that the Erasmus+ programme continues to attract higher education institutions, the number of participants increased substantially in 2017, and over 4 000 higher education institutions and mobility consortia were awarded mobility grants.

It is undeniable that internationalisation can lead to a diverse set of desirable outcomes and impacts regarding the operation of higher education institutions and academics' professional development, but it must be noted that universities are often considering such indicators like proportions of international staff, number of international students, research papers published with a co-author from another country etc., which limits our understanding of the possible supporting and hindering factors behind internationalisation. In order to better encompass internationalisation, the evolution of institutions, structures, systems, functions, governance, administration and financing issues and the complex and interdependent nature of

the positive and less positive dimensions of internationalisation must be considered as well (Wihlborg & Robson, 2017).

While there are many aspects of internationalisation, this report only focuses on academics' mobility and in particular, teaching mobility. Although it is our understanding that internationalisation at home and internationalisation abroad initiatives should be considered comprehensively. In our report, we put a special focus on the important role of academics' mobility as a crucial factor in driving the internationalisation agenda (de Wit et al., 2015). Considering staff mobility in recent years, we see an increasing tendency in European countries to utilize both incoming and outgoing mobility as it is demonstrated by data from the European Tertiary Education Register (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The number of incoming and outgoing staff mobilities in the European countries between 2014 and 2016 (Data source: European Tertiary Education Register).

3.5 RESEARCH ON TEACHING MOBILITY

Generally, staff mobility is given less focus in research regarding the internationalisation of higher education and also, institutional strategies seem to be rarely systematic in promoting this opportunity (de Wit et al., 2015), and it is rarely recognised towards career progression (Racké, 2013). Previous research uncovered that a strategic approach to academic mobility has clear advantages for research, teaching and professional development (Colucci, Ferencz, Gaebel & Wächter, 2014; Svetlik & Braček Lalić, 2016). The strategic role of academic mobility was reassured by Postiglione and Altbach (2013) as well. Teaching mobility can also play an important role in joint programmes, and through those, in the internationalisation at home agenda of institutions (Erdei et al., 2018).

Despite its strategic importance and possible impacts, outcomes assessment of staff mobility strongly focuses on input and output indicators and lacking important contextual and

process elements (*Deardoff & van Gaalen, 2012; Chang & Lin, 2018*). Therefore, a more rigorous and complex measurement regarding the topic is needed, e.g. from a quality assurance perspective (*Voroshilova, 2015; Hauptman Komotar, 2018*), taking into consideration personality factors (*Dewey & Duff, 2009; Li & Tu, 2016*) and the pedagogical dimension as well (*Wihlborg, 2009*).

In recent years, large investigations and EU projects aimed to assess the impacts of staff mobility such as Erasmus Impact Study, REALISE, Equatic, Valera and MORE3. These projects mainly emphasize the role of staff mobility in internationalisation efforts as well as its benefits for the participants themselves. However, previous research often analysed staff mobility which includes both academic and non-academic (staff training) mobility in higher education. In terms of evidence, the Erasmus Impact Study in 2016 demonstrated that teaching staff mobility not only promotes the internationalisation of HEIs through cooperation among institutions, but it also promotes internationalisation at home for non-mobile students and boosts institutional innovations (e.g. teaching methods, curricula, and good practices). As for the numbers, 81% of mobile academic staff reported positive effects on the quality of their teaching and on multi-disciplinary and cross-organisational teaching cooperation; 86% of mobile staff agreed that mobility improves international collaboration with partner HEIs, and 95% of HEI managers regarded staff mobility as pivotal in support of internationalisation at home (*Ball, 2019*). A study led at the Middlesex University on the impacts of Erasmus+ staff mobility further examined questions on gained competences regarding personal and professional development and both outbound teaching and training mobility participants reported increased job satisfaction and extended professional network in 2016 (94.74% and 100% respectively) (*Ball, 2019*).

The REALISE project aimed at assessing the impact of Erasmus+ staff mobility on both individuals and institutions by focusing on three objectives: impact (awareness of the added value), implementation (identify and develop innovative practices) and recognition (fostering the recognition and career development) (*Ball, 2019*). However, according to the REALISE report, teaching mobility is still somewhat considered as the „poor sister” of mobility programmes (*Ball, 2019*). 10 universities from 10 different countries with more than 6000 respondents participated in the REALISE project, and despite the contextual diversity of the partner countries, the overall conclusion of the report was that structural changes should be implemented in order to improve the recognition of teaching staff mobility. In fact, the institutional recognition of mobility experiences largely divided the respondents (694 interviewees reported major recognition, 703 minor or no recognition, and 538 neutral recognition). (*Ball 2019*). Another obstacle that the report mentions is closely related to the implementation of mobility programmes: mobility management, including often insufficient funding and heavy workload at the sending institution, or poor visibility of the mobility opportunities are factors that often create obstacles for mobility participants (REALISE Report). As a policy recommendation, the project also published a toolbox based on the participants’ responses, and in the matter of institutional recognition, good practices were highlighted such as the recognition of mobility as training hours in the teachers’ work plan, or the implementation of a ‘recognition table’ with different grades for evaluation by the host institution regarding the performance of mobility participants.

The MORE3 study initiated by the European Commission focused instead on the role of academic mobility in expanding researchers' network. The study aimed at developing policy measures for creating an open labour market for researchers in the European Research Area (ERA) therefore the assessment of mobility indicators (analyzed in the previous study of MORE2) are rather directed towards increasing the attractiveness of research careers (*European Commission, 2017*). An important finding of the MORE studies is that the main drive for researchers and academics to become „mobile” is to gain research autonomy and a certain balance of teaching and research, oftentimes even by giving up some salary in exchange for higher quality-working conditions relevant for scientific productivity and advancement (*European Commission, 2017*). Furthermore, the authors summarized that in order to make the EU more attractive for the researcher community, more favourable working conditions are needed that could properly serve individual research agendas; and this fact requires a stronger policy focus on boosting conditions for scientific productivity in all Member States (*European Commission, 2017*).

The project called eQuATIC (Assessing quality of partnerships amongst Higher Education Institutions) took a different approach in developing a quality assessment tool that aims to monitor objectively the strengths and weaknesses of international cooperations and partnerships². In order to better understand the impact of staff mobility, eQuATIC involved the use of quantified indicators based on previous data and turned data into figures to monitor each phase of international partnerships. To make an example, the project focused on innovative tools such as developing new ways for peer- and self-assessment.

The VALERA study, besides assessing the benefits of student mobility, examined the professional impact of Erasmus staff mobility in the views of mobile teachers and university leaders (*Engel, 2010*). The study resulted in considerable variation of the data between the different countries that participated in the programme, and the most remarkable differences can be observed through the feedback from respondents of Western European countries and Eastern European countries. For example, participating in a teaching mobility was evaluated more favourably by teachers from Central or Eastern European countries, and most significantly there is a difference regarding the evaluation of the impact of teaching mobility on the individual's career perspectives. The heterogeneity of different countries and how data differs by countries also brings attention to economic differences that impact funding, institutional mechanisms and the extent to which mobility experiences could influence individual professional careers.

3.6 THE IMPACTS OF TEACHING MOBILITY

The primary focus of staff mobility, as Engel (2010) states, is not the promotion of the teachers' professional career, but to foster the learning conditions of mobile as well as non-mobile students at both home and host institution, even though this Erasmus experience might also have an influence on the teachers' competences and on their individual career (*Engel, 2010, p. 2*). So how we could assess the most relevant impacts of teaching mobility? Most importantly,

² For more information: www.equatic.ugent.be.

as previous research showed, measuring the impact of the teaching period abroad should differentiate between the impact on the individual and on the host and sending institution.

According to the Valera study on Erasmus teaching mobility, the most beneficial impacts on the individual level are enhanced intercultural understanding (92%), intensified use of scientific foreign-language publications for teaching (71%), new cooperations at the host institution (66%), improved research contacts (64%), and an overall enhanced knowledge about higher education (*Engel, 2010*). Besides, getting more experience in new ways of teaching and learning or getting to know different quality assurance procedures were mentioned frequently by teacher respondents from Central and Eastern Europe (*Engel, 2010*). However, a study led by Janson et al (2009) reveals that the impact of mobility has considerable differences by the teaching subjects: the most positive impacts are reported by teachers from agriculture (69%) art and design (67%), geography (65%), and medicine (64%) meanwhile such impact is less relevant in teaching mathematics (35%), law (30%) and communication science (29%) (*Janson et al., 2009*). The mentioned study also highlights the most mentioned positive individual impacts by teacher respondents such as the development of new study concepts and contents, and the increase of comparative approaches in teaching.

As for the home institutions, the impacts of teaching mobility are generally considered beneficial according to the research findings. Although university leaders rather underline the positive impacts regarding the international reputation and scientific prestige of the institution and less impact on improved teaching methods of mobile teachers. Another interesting finding of the Valera study is that teachers consider teaching mobility as an individual activity which is only valued to a certain extent. To support this fact, the majority of teacher respondents underlined that “teaching abroad means extra work without any compensation at the home institution...thus that the appreciation of such mobility might not be communicated in an appropriate way” (*Engel, 2010*). In view of this finding, institutional recognition of teaching mobility and its added values needs to be enhanced at the home institutions. In addition, mobile teachers were usually not satisfied with the administrative and financial support of their departments and that “only 12% (of university leader respondents) states that efforts are made to find replacements at home for the mobile teachers (*Engel, 2010*).

4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research involved a mixed-methods strategy, combining qualitative and quantitative tools to have a broader understanding of the research questions. A preliminary, qualitative-focused research was applied in order to map the basic domains that could be involved in a large scale survey. The consortium concluded 33 semi-structured interviews altogether with various stakeholders in teaching mobility (academics who were already participated in teaching mobility and those who haven't, administrators, decision makers, students). (The pre-survey semi-structured interview protocol is available in Appendix 2). Besides the interviews a focus-group was organised where participants (academics, administrators interested in teaching mobility) shared their experiences through an intensive customer journey mapping process.

Based on the results of the preliminary research, we have created an online survey instrument to explore the landscape of teaching mobility. The basic structure and scales used in the survey will be presented below. After the survey a second set of semi-structured interviews were conducted in order to have a better understanding regarding the descriptive results and main findings of the quantitative analysis. (The post-survey semi-structured interview protocol is available in Appendix 3).

The survey (see in Appendix 4) comprises of four blocks, one of which is for only those who have participated in teaching mobility before. Therefore, the research encompasses the experiences of those who have not participated in teaching mobility before in the hope of discovering the main barriers of abstaining as well.

The general structure of the questionnaire makes it possible to gather relevant organisational contextual data, data regarding personal aspects and factors related to a concrete mobility experience. A unique part of the survey is the third block, where we ask participants to think about a concrete mobility experience they had and the survey guides them to better focus on that memory with few introductory questions (e.g. when and where was the mobility). This would allow us to gather more specific data, tied to a real experience instead of a general approach.

In the survey, we implemented several standardized scales that have been used in previous research which would allow us an international and intersectoral comparison. The following scales are used:

- **Dimensions of the Learning Organisation Questionnaire** (Marsick & Watkins, 2003): the 21 items measure workplace learning, organizational culture, structure and processes and organizational learning on the individual, group and institutional level. The research in using the DLOQ instrument in higher education is quite extensive (*Abu-Tineh, 2011; Akhtar & Khan, 2011; Ali & Khamis Ali, 2012; Chawla & Lenka, 2015; Ghomshi et al., 2018; Holyoke, Sturko, Wood, & Wu, 2012; Kim, Egan, & Tolson, 2015; Kumar, 2005; Nazari & Pihie, 2012; Ponnuswamy & Manohar, 2014; Rowe, 2010; Salleh & Huang, 2011; Song, Chermack, & Kim, 2013; Watkins & Dirani, 2013*)
- **International orientation and strategy of the institution**: the items are taken from a dimension of the HEInnovate tool (an initiative of the European Commission's DG Education and Culture in partnership with the OECD Local Economic and Employment Development Programme (LEED)) which aims to provide a diagnostic

assessment of higher education institutions regarding their innovative and entrepreneurial operation.

- **Personality factors:** inclusion of these scales was supported by the methodology of the Erasmus Impact Study (*CHE Consult et al., 2014*) which also uses personality factors as exploratory variables in assessing mobility experiences. Based on the interviews Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (*Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004*), ambiguity tolerance (*Herman et al., 2010*) and self-efficacy (*Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995*).

The main areas of the survey are on teaching mobility. Several items deal with the possible barriers and restraining factors (questions for both target groups), another set of questions deal with the source of information regarding teaching mobility and the respondent's satisfaction with this. For those who have participated in teaching mobility, concrete questions are dealing with their satisfaction with different elements of the programme, their intention to return or to go on another mobility, feedback they have received, main influencing factors in the decision and identified outcomes and impacts based on the three missions of higher education and personal and professional development.

The general demographic and institutional context questions will allow us to explore different types of institutions and individuals based on their attitudes and opinions of teaching mobility. For example, the type of institution (public or private, more or less internationalised institutions), senior and junior faculty, language barriers etc.

This survey will allow us to explore the following broad research questions and aims which will be examined via exploratory and multivariate statistical procedures:

- 6) What are the main differences between higher education systems, different types of institutions and different individuals regarding their attitudes and experiences towards teaching mobility?
- 7) What are the main outcomes and impacts of teaching mobility?
- 8) What are the main factors that could restrain individuals from engaging in teaching mobility?
- 9) What are the main factors that influence individuals' willingness to participate in and satisfaction with teaching mobility?
- 10) What are the main factors that influence the possible outcomes of teaching mobility?

Our data gathering aimed for a wide range of higher education institutions in all the involved countries via national agencies in order to maximise the variance in our sample. The main aim was to reach at least 500 participants from different Erasmus+ Programme Country in order to be able to generate meaningful groupings and comparisons during the data analysis. Signaling the significance of the topic, at the end of the data gathering we have managed to surpass our initial goal regarding the number of participants (N=745, which will be detailed later).

The research project is approved by the Research Ethics Board of the Faculty of Education and Psychology of Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE). The research is planned and executed by concerning general standards for social sciences and humanities research (regarding human participation) and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDRP).

5 DESCRIPTIVE RESULTS

5.1 RESULTS OF THE PRELIMINARY INTERVIEWS AND FOCUS GROUP

At the beginning of the project, we employed an explorative qualitative strategy in order to uncover basic factors regarding teaching mobility as literature in the topic were scarce. The main aim of the first part of IO1 was to gather a wide range of experience regarding teaching mobility, therefore we planned the interviews and the focus group around different topics regarding teaching mobility: popularity, barriers, possible benefits, motivation and expectations, dissemination, suggestions.

We conducted semi-structured interviews with academics who have already participated in teaching mobility and with those who haven't. We selected students whose teachers were on teaching mobility and also, administrative staff members as well, who are dealing with issues regarding teaching mobility. Altogether we worked with 33 interviews from different national and organisational context. Applying a content analysis approach, we identified central themes in the interviews that were incorporated in our survey (e.g. motivational factors, hindering factors).

Besides the interviews, a focus group activity was planned in the project that was held in Budapest from the 28th February 2019 to 4th March 2019 with participants from different countries, both academics and administrative staff as well. The focus group was organised as a training activity which aimed to explore participants thoughts, attitudes and experiences regarding teaching mobility. The focus group employed a user experience research approach, putting the respondents into the viewpoints of academics who would go on teaching mobility. The main output of the focus group was different user personas (stereotypical "customers" of teaching mobilities, see for example Figure 2 and with the help of these personas, we tried to solve their problems, tried to motivate them to go on a teaching mobility and overall engage them in the process, thus creating a customer journey map, see for example Appendix 1. (Følstad & Kvale, 2018). The user personas and customer journey maps were digitalized using Uxpressia³. The experiences of the focus group were also incorporated in the survey development.

³ www.uxpressia.com

Figure 2. A hypothetical user persona for an academic who would go on teaching mobility as developed by participants at the focus group. [Link to larger image.](#) (Uxpressia template; photo from pixabay).

The interviews emphasized that teaching mobility is especially popular among junior staff and departments of languages. Interviewees often addressed the issues of the lack of confidence in one’s language skills (ranging from a feeling of insecurity and fear to an actual lack of knowledge) which can be connected to academic teaching skills as well. Others voiced that teaching mobility is seen as a small scale issue, not important regarding academic advancement, therefore underutilized.

During the interviews, we have gathered lots of possible problems, barriers or challenges regarding teaching mobility but often found that these aspects could be subject to change (what is a problem in a context is not a problem in another). Barriers came up regarding personal issues (laziness, fear, language barriers, leaving family), resource issues (time, financial), organisation and administration (lack of communication, information, problems of

finding hosts, hard to organize 8 hours etc.), communication and information (late answer, lack of openness etc.), organisational support and strategy (lack of internal strategy, not worth financially for the institution, lack of recognition in advancement etc.) system or cultural issues (different educational system, different students, different disciplinary approach etc.).

Regarding possible benefits, results of teaching mobility, interviewees also provided a wide range of possibilities. Results could be categorized regarding learning and teaching (e.g. joint practicum, development in pedagogical skills, better understanding of students, developing educational materials or courses), research (scientific cooperation, joint publication, conferences, feedback on topic, access to host's infrastructure etc.), third mission (scientific knowledge dissemination for public audience), professional development (networking, CV, benefits in advancement), personal development (development in stress management, flexibility, interpersonal competences, language skills, cooperation skills, seeing and getting to know other culture and education system, work-culture etc.), organisational-strategic aspects (new joint programmes, impact on student mobility, introduction of a new course/module, increased reputation, internationalization).

What drives interviewees to participate in teaching mobility can be described via personal motivations (love to travel, curiosity, get to know other culture) and professional development (research, new partners, development of language skills, self-reflection regarding teaching, professional inquiry regarding the host's curriculum). Also, expectations are important factors of motivation and satisfaction: to be well organized, be a rich professional experience (not only lectures but visiting other lectures, professional discussion with colleagues), settle details in time, the host should promote the lecture and receive more feedback.

Regarding dissemination, it mostly happens in informal settings if it ever happens. Interviewees addressed the lack of dissemination regarding teaching mobility. Where it happens it usually informal (informal chat between colleagues, lecturer mentions it during faculty meeting). There are some cases and good practices where some formal opportunity is organized for dissemination (deliberately planning time for the report during faculty meetings, organising round table regarding the topic).

Interviewees had a lot of ideas regarding possible ways to develop teaching mobility. We have categorized these suggestions as organisational/administrative aspects (eg. digital database of host institutions, ongoing submission, increase budget, bonus for host teacher, job shadowing, transparent assessment criteria) and institutional/strategic aspects (better support from department, organise Erasmus lecturer course or week for possible incoming lecturers every semester, give more recognition, provide preparation training, organise knowledge-sharing events). Participants directly addressed the need for a digital database that contains possible opportunities to participate in teaching mobility which is searchable by disciplinary field and also indicates what field or what knowledge does the host require. Also, it would be beneficial if the database could contain information regarding the curriculum, compatibility of HE system (e.g. organising of teaching time etc.).

Other aspects emerged, like the perception of the sending country in the host country (which could impact the likelihood of cooperation). For teaching mobility to be successful, interviewees voiced that the academics must prepare in advance for their teaching (e.g. looking through the curriculum of the host institution) and they must have a risk-taking personality. It seems that teaching mobility needs proactivity because it is rare that a host institution directly invites somebody, so the teachers must search for opportunities themselves. There were some negative experiences as well when there were disagreements regarding professional content, where the academics didn't recognize each others competence or autonomy (too tight control regarding what to teach) which could hinder the teaching mobility experience.

Based on the results of our interviews and focus group, we created an online survey in Hungarian and English language as well which was administered to academics all over Europe with the help of our partners. The next chapters will detail the descriptive results of the survey.

5.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE SURVEY SAMPLE

After data-cleaning, the final database contained responses from 745 academics from European HEIs. As a direct consequence of the data-gathering method, most of the respondents are from Hungary (21,8%), but other countries are represented as well (Slovakia – 13,2%; Croatia – 9,6%; Italy – 8,8%; Spain – 6% and Sweden – 5,6%). The sample seems to be fairly balanced as it contains responses from West-, Central-, North- and Eastern-Europe as well (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Respondents by country of origin.

In this study, we consider two levels as units of analysis: organizational and individual. Regarding organizations, academics in the sample are mainly from state or public HEIs (94,1%) and only 5,9% of the sample is from non-state or private HEIs. The institutions in our sample have different foci (Figure 4): 56,2% of respondents are working for large, research-oriented universities, 24,4% for general, small- or medium-sized institutions. A small portion of academics are working for institutions that are providing special, focused education (8,3%) or for institutions with a vocational focus (8,8%). HEIs in the sample are mainly large universities, considering the number of students (53,6% of respondents reported that they are working at a university with more than 10000 students), while 27,8% of respondents are coming from a university with 2500-10000 students, 16,2% are from universities with 500-2500 students and only 2,4% of respondents are from small universities with less than 500 students.

Figure 4. Respondents by type of HEI.

The survey gathered information regarding individual-level variables as well. Considering general demographic variables, 42,2% of the respondents are male, while 57,8% are female.

Figure 5. Academic rank of respondents.

The 4,5% of respondents are fairly young (under 30), while the majority are between 31-40 (27,8%), 41-50 (33,9%) and 51-60 (24,7%) and another small portion are above 61 (9,1%). Compared to this, 20% of respondents are working for less than 5 years in their current institution, 19,5% between 5-10 years, 22,2% between 11-15 years, 16,4% between 15-20 years, 9,9% between 21-25 years and 12,4% are working at their current institution for more than 25 years. Somewhat in correlation with age and tenure, respondents are mainly assistant professors (31%), while 28,1% are associate professors and 23,2% are professors (11,9% are distinguished professors or professors with chair) (Figure 5).

Respondents are fairly balanced regarding disciplinary orientation (Figure 6). Most of the participants are from the field of social sciences (34,9%) and humanities (21,9%), while engineering disciplines are represented by 18,2% of the sample. A small portion of respondents are working with natural sciences (8,9%), health- and medical sciences (7,4%) and agriculture and veterinary (1,5%). It was our hypothesis that the nature of the discipline would be an important factor from a mobility point of view, so respondents were asked to categorize their field by specific categories. Nearly half of the sample put their disciplines into these special categories. 21,6% stated that their discipline is rather nationally embedded (e.g. law, education), while 20,7% considered their discipline as containing regional relevance (e.g. regional studies, geography) that could transcend the limitations of borders and language. Finally, 18,1% respondent stated that their discipline is dealing with a foreign language as these would be natural partners in mobility schemes. These categories weren't mutually exclusive, so respondents could have chosen more than one category to describe their discipline.

Figure 6. Disciplinary fields of respondents.

International experience is an important characteristic of the sample. The sample contains academics that have already participated in teaching mobility (69%) and those who haven't participated yet (31%) which would be an important dimension to compare. Apart from this specific type of international experience, it is clear that our sample contains academics that have significant experience in international settings. 85,6% of respondents have already participated in international conferences, while 54,7% have participated in research mobility programmes, 44,2% participated in some kind of intensive programme or cooperated in international projects, 34,2% had experiences in longer, study mobility programmes and 46,4% of respondents indicated some other international experience.

Although our study is not based on a representative sample, for the sake of the explorative nature of this research we can say that we have a fairly balanced sample which contains different perspectives that are worth exploring regarding teaching mobility and these data could provide valuable insights for developing a quality tool for teaching mobility as well.

5.3 STRATEGIC APPROACH TO AND ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT OF INTERNATIONALISATION

The survey contained questions regarding the assessment of perceived support of internationalisation, strategic approach of the topic and other aspects of the area (e.g. the number of international programmes and students). Perceived organisational support of internationalisation consisted of seven items, developed based on the results of preliminary

interviews and focus group. The items regarding the strategic approach to internationalisation (6 items) were adopted from the HEInnovate⁴ “The Internationalised Institution” scale. Each item was rated on a 5-points Likert-scale by respondents, which was transformed into a 3-points scale for this report (rather not true: 1, 2; neutral: 3; rather true: 4, 5).

Overall, it seems that respondents feel that their organisation supports teaching mobility as academics have the opportunity to organise their classes in a way that they could go on a teaching mobility (65,3% of respondents stated that this is rather true in their university), and they feel supported in their endeavours (63,9% showed positive orientation towards this statement). Besides the reported positive atmosphere regarding support of internationalisation, it seems when substitutions come into question, respondents are less likely to report positive attitudes (39,8% of respondents stated that if he/she would miss a class at home due to being on teaching mobility, the organisation wouldn’t provide a substitution). Furthermore, it seems that teaching mobility is not well-recognized in academics’ career development (23,9% of respondents were not agreeing to the statement that teaching mobility is a recognized activity in their organisation) (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Organisational support of internationalisation.

⁴ <https://heinnovate.eu/en/about>

Regarding internationalisation strategies (Figure 8) it seems, that in line with global trends, internationalisation became an integral part of HEIs operation, 76% of respondents stated that internationalisation is an important part of the institution’s strategy and 68% perceived that they have some kind of incentive of support mechanisms in place for this field. Although the recruitment of international staff members is not that prevalent (23,9% disagrees with the statement that their organisation is trying to attract academics and staff member with international orientation).

Figure 8. Strategic approach to internationalisation.

The survey aimed to explore the international experiences of the universities where the respondents are currently employed (Figure 9). Respondents were asked to estimate the number of international programmes that are run by their HEI and the ratio of international students compared to domestic students. From these data, we have a simple overview of the international embeddedness and orientation of the universities. According to our data, most of the HEIs have well developed international programmes and have a significant amount of international students, making them well-established institutions in terms of internationalisation. This would mean that our sample is somewhat biased towards those institutions that are already aware of the benefits of internationalisation.

Figure 9. Ratio of international programmes and students.

Regarding HEIs orientation towards internationalisation, other important aspects can be considered as well. In the survey respondents had to report the sources of information where they hear about mobility opportunities and rate their satisfaction with the given method of communication at their HEIs (Figure 10). The form of communication is dominantly informal (60,7%) as stated by respondents, and it is also important, that 15,9% of respondents stated that they don't receive information regarding mobility experiences. The most prevalent information sources are e-mails (79,7%), webpage (61,3%), but informal communication also plays an important role (44,4%) and it seems that respondents are mainly satisfied with these opportunities (64,9% reported that they are rather satisfied).

Figure 10. Source of information and satisfaction with dissemination.

Majority of respondents feel that international mobility is an expectation towards them (49,46%), while 24,96% feels that participating in mobility programmes are somewhat expected from them and 25,58% reported that they do not feel such a pressure towards themselves. Compared to this, 53% of respondents stated that they are intended to go on a teaching mobility in the following years (sum of respondents who indicated 9 or 10 on a 10-point scale), 21% indicated a somewhat unsure position, that there is a chance that they will go on a teaching mobility in the following years (responses of 7 and 8), while only 26% stated that they are not considering teaching mobility in the near future (respondents between 0-6) (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Intention to go on a teaching mobility.

5.4 HINDERING FACTORS

One of the main parts of the questionnaire focused on possible hindering factors that could prohibit academics from participating in teaching mobility programmes. Items listed in these questions were informed by literature and from the experiences of the explorative interviews and focus group as well. The most important hindering factors (Figure 12) reported by participants are considering the administrative and organization tasks regarding mobility. 30,55% of respondents stated that it is a great inconvenience to organise and realise teaching mobility, while 28,32% fear that the budget won't be enough to cover their expenses, 26,4% has issues with solving their substitution at their home university for the duration of the mobility. Nearly a quarter of the respondents simply can't find the time to participate in such activities. It seems that lack of pedagogical competences, foreign language skills and a lack of opportunities in the languages known by the respondents are less of an issue (more than 80% of respondents stated that these are not an issue for them). The 5 most dominant hindering factors are summarized in the graph below, while the full summary is in the appendix.

Figure 12. Most important hindering factors.

In order to have a clearer picture regarding hindering factors, we employed data reduction methods (exploratory factor analysis) to uncover the latent structure between variables describing hindering factors. We used a Maximum Likelihood extraction method and Varimax rotation and no items were excluded due to small communality. Finally, 5 factors were extracted explaining 61,65% of the total variance⁵. The rotated factor matrix is presented in the next table and regression scores were saved for later use (Figure 13).

⁵ Other statistics regarding the exploratory factor analysis were adequate: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy: 0,921; Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: $\chi^2(276) = 5452,66$; $p < 0,001$. Goodness-of-fit Test: $\chi^2(166) = 523,92$; $p < 0,001$.

Items	Factor 1: Lack of time and financial support	Factor 2: Lack of connections and reputation or communication issues	Factor 3: Lack of competence and motivation	Factor 4: Intercultural difficulties	Factor 5: No benefits
It is hard for me to plan this opportunity ahead.	0,673				
I have no time to participate in such activities.	0,654				
I can't solve my substitution at my workplace.	0,591				
I fear that the budget available in the programme wouldn't be enough.	0,556				
It comes with great inconvenience to organise and execute it.	0,485				
I can't finance my mobility in advance.	0,471				
I find administrative tasks regarding teaching mobility quite complicated.	0,444	0,394			
I don't want to leave my family even for a short period of time.	0,409		0,336		
I don't have adequate contacts.		0,722			
It is hard to communicate with the host institution.		0,625			
I'm not a well-known academic in my field yet for host institutions to accept me.		0,616			
I don't have enough information regarding the opportunity.		0,601			
It would be hard for me to organize the required number of lessons.	0,356	0,389			
I'm not confident enough in my foreign language skills.			0,688		
I'm not confident enough in my pedagogical competences.		0,328	0,585		
I prefer someone else to seize the opportunity			0,523		
There are no opportunities in those languages that I speak.			0,505		
I don't have any motivation to participate.			0,504		0,337
Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different needs and expectations of students.			0,350	0,744	
Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different national/educational systems.				0,694	0,312
Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different research / disciplinary culture of the host institution.			0,387	0,621	
Teaching mobility doesn't play an important role in my professional development.					0,693
In my organisation, teaching mobility is not a priority.					0,666
I wouldn't be able to take advantage of the experience at my home institution.			0,329		0,479

Figure 13. Rotated factor matrix of items regarding hindering factors.

An important question in our research project was revolved around the possible hindering factors. As this question appeared to those who have already participated in teaching mobility and for those who haven't yet, this will enable us to conduct interesting comparisons between these two groups. The results of this analysis will be presented in the next section.

5.5 BACKGROUND INFORMATION ON REPORTED TEACHING MOBILITIES

The next section of the survey contained a conditional branch. Respondents were asked whether or not they were one a teaching mobility. The following questions (background information on the mobility experience, mobility factors, satisfaction with the experience and results and feedback sections) were only asked from those who have already participated in teaching mobility. The survey explicitly asked respondents to think about a certain teaching mobility experience and answer the questions in light of that specific experience. With this solution, the researchers tried to influence respondents in a way that they focus on a specific experience rather than generalities. To help respondents focus, the survey asked for some specifications regarding their teaching mobility experience (when and where did it happen, how long it was, what language did the respondent had to use, what kind of agreement were between the two institutions before the mobility).

Our database is fairly balanced as the survey managed to reach a considerable number of academics who haven't participated in teaching mobility (31%, N=204), although most of the sample consists of academics who have already been on teaching mobility (69%, N=455). Most of the teaching mobilities reported in our survey were quite recent, 65,9% of them were realized in 2018 and 2019, but the database contains experiences as far back as 2009 (2,97%) (Figure 14).

Notes. Y-axis shows valid % of respondents, value labels are the actual number of respondents)

Figure 14. General data regarding participatin in teaching mobility.

As our sample is not representative, it is still indicative of our sample, therefore we report the destinations that our respondents chose for their teaching mobility. The most frequent countries are Spain, Poland, France, Germany and Portugal (covering 36,7% of valid responses). The whole distribution is reported in the appendix. The majority of our respondents spoke in English when they were on their teaching mobility (74,8%), and only a handful of academics were able to conduct their mobility in other languages (e.g. German – 4,1%; French – 3,8%; Spanish – 3,2%).

We also asked respondents to state how long was their teaching mobility (Figure 15). Usually, the programme allows for a minimum of 2 days, maximum of 2 months of stay (between partner countries). Usually, respondents are aimed for shorter stays, 87,3% of respondents stated that their mobility lasted between 2-5 days and only 12,7% stayed for a longer period (10,4% for 2-4 weeks, 2,3% for 6-8 weeks). This means, that most of the respondents completed their required 8 hours of teaching in between 2-5 days, which requires a considerable amount of organization from the side of the host institution as well for the academics to realize their teaching mobility.

Figure 15. Duration of teaching mobility.

Figure 16. Mobility context.

Finally, we surveyed the preliminary conditions between the host and home institutions regarding respondents' specific teaching mobility experience (Figure 16). It could be an important dimension, whether the specific mobility experience was realized in a context where agreement between the two institutions was already in place, compared to a situation where the agreement was made especially for the sake of the reported mobility. The sample seems to be fairly balanced regarding the given categories: 14,7% of respondents stated that their reported teaching mobility was realized between institutions that didn't have prior agreements before the experience, 30,9% stated that the institutions had the agreement, but there was no teaching mobility exchange before the reported one in the relations of the two institutions. Those, who have reported an existing agreement and prior teaching mobilities between the institutions (either by a colleague of the respondent or the respondents themselves repeating the mobility) makes the 30,4% and 22,8% of the sample.

The following sections will deal with specifications regarding the mobilities reported in this sub-section. The survey explored academics motivation, satisfaction and perceived results regarding these experiences.

5.6 MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS

In order for us to understand the dynamics of participation in a teaching mobility programme, it is important to have a look at the different drivers that could influence academics in their decision. Based on the results of the preliminary interviews and focus group, we identified 15 items that could describe the possible range of motivations. The items were rated on a scale of 1 (not important) to 5 (very important) based on the perception of respondents regarding how significant the given statement was in their decision to go on teaching mobility (reminder: these questions were answered by those who have already participated in teaching mobility). Simplifying the presentation of results, we merged the categories as before (1-2: not important; 3: somewhat important, 4-5: very important). The most important and least important factors will be presented here (Figure 17). The full list of factors is presented in the Appendix 5.

Figure 17. The least and most important motivations for participation.

The data tells us, that academics who have participated in teaching mobility were mainly motivated by their inner curiosity to learn new educational practices (84,4% felt that this was very important motivation for them), and to learn about the research projects of the host institution (81,3% found it very important), but also the possibilities for joint-projects played an important role in their decision (81,9% found it very important). It is evident that teaching mobility is influenced by other factors than educational purposes. On the other side, it seems that expectations or encouragement from the organisation or the leadership is simply not that

important (55,6% and 53,1% stated that these factors were not important in their decision), also which is quite contradictory to our expectations, recommendations from colleagues proved to be a weak factor as well (45,6% stated that this was not important). From these results, it seems that the decision to go on teaching mobility is influenced by internal rather than external factors.

We used data reduction techniques here as well for us to be able to present a more focused analysis of the different groups regarding their motivation. We used a Principal Component Analysis approach with Varimax rotation⁶. The 4 principal components extracted explained 70,54% of the total variance. The rotated component matrix is presented in the next table and regression scores were saved for later use (Figure 18).

Items	Factor 1: Learning (languages, pedagogical methods)	Factor 2: Getting to know new places, cultures	Factor 3: Research opportunities	Factor 4: Expectation, urge
To improve my competencies in teaching in a foreign language	0,901			
To try out myself in a foreign language environment	0,850			
To improve my foreign language skills	0,826			
To improve my general pedagogical competencies	0,739			
I wanted to learn about the culture of the host country		0,844		
I wanted to learn about the higher education system of the host country		0,782	0,308	
I wanted to learn about the educational practices at the host institution		0,743		
I love to travel		0,696		
Possible research opportunities			0,885	
Possible opportunities for joint-projects			0,855	
I wanted to learn about the research projects of the host institution		0,405	0,766	
Encouragement from the leadership				0,873
Expectation from my organisation				0,858
Recommendation from a colleague				0,761
A previous teaching mobility experience				0,429

Figure 18. Rotated component matrix of items regarding motivational factors.

Using the extracted principal components will allow us to present a more focused analysis of the issues regarding participants motivation. Next, we will deal with outcome variables regarding the specific teaching mobility experience, namely satisfaction and results.

⁶ Other statistics regarding the principal component analysis were adequate: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy: 0,820; Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: $\chi^2(105) = 3091,04$; $p < 0,001$.

5.7 SATISFACTION WITH THE REPORTED TEACHING MOBILITY EXPERIENCE

In order to have a broad understanding of the quality of teaching mobilities, we asked respondents to rate their reported teaching mobility based on their satisfaction with different elements of the programme and the process. The answers were clustered to reflect the percentage of respondents who are not satisfied, somewhat satisfied and rather satisfied with the given item (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Satisfaction with teaching mobility experience.

It seems that those who have participated in teaching mobilities reported a rather high satisfaction regarding different elements of the programme. Respondents were most satisfied with the help they received from the host institution organising the mobility (82,91% were rather satisfied with this element), and with the time frame of the mobility (81,03% were rather satisfied). Academics were least satisfied with the administrative process (only 66,82% reported that they are rather satisfied) and the amount of financial support (only 66,44% reported that they are rather satisfied). These latter numbers are not alarmingly low, but compared to other aspects, they scored lower.

Besides the specific elements, the survey also measured respondents' general satisfaction with their teaching mobility experience using a Net Promoter Score (NPS) approach. The general idea of the method is to ask respondent (customers) how likely that they would recommend the company/product/service to a friend or a colleague on a scale of 0-10. In our case, we used two questions: "Considering all important factors, how satisfied were you with the teaching mobility you have experienced?" and "Would you be willing to repeat the teaching mobility experience under the same conditions?". Based on the NPS approach, respondents who gave a score of 0-6 are grouped as "Detractors", those who gave 7 or 8 are

grouped as “Passive” and those, who scored 9 or 10 are belong to the “Promoter” category. The NPS is calculated by subtracting the percentage of detractors from the percentage of promoters. The calculation can yield a number in the range of -100 and 100 and generally a result higher than 0 is considered good, while a result above 50 is excellent, and a result above 70 is exceptional (Reichheld, 2003).

Considering the overall satisfaction of respondents with their teaching mobility experience, it seems that they rated it as excellent, as it is evident from the reported NPS values (56 and 63,4 for overall satisfaction and return-intent respectively). The intention to repeat the mobility (with the same conditions) could signal a strong commitment towards the experience and in return, a strong indicator for satisfaction (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Net Promoter Score of different aspects of teaching mobility.

Besides satisfaction measures, the survey directly aimed to explore respondents’ perception regarding the possible outcomes and results of their teaching mobility experience, along with the feedback they received for their work.

5.8 FEEDBACK ON AND RESULTS OF REPORTED TEACHING MOBILITIES

Before engaging with results, we focus on the feedback that the individual academics received during their mobility as these could be an important source for drawing conclusions regarding the possible impacts and results of teaching mobilities. We listed several dimensions which respondents could have rated along with the usefulness of feedback they received (from students and colleagues from the host institutions) – if any (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Feedback from students and from colleagues.

Respondents reported more frequent and useful feedback from their peers in the host institution, but it must be noted, that students are also an important source of information regarding teaching method, the content of the lecture, teaching style and usefulness as well. Overall, it seems that there are a considerable amount of respondents (25,6%-50,6% haven't received feedback from students, 17,2%-43,2% haven't received feedback from colleagues) who haven't received any feedback regarding their activities during the mobility. How these feedbacks can be harnessed or made more useful is another question that we will cover later.

In the survey, we used items describing potential results that we identified through the preliminary interviews and focus group. Initially, we clustered results around broader topics: education (8 items), research (9 items), professional development (14 items) and organisational results (7 items).

Figure 22. The most and least important results of teaching mobilities.

The diagram above (Figure 22) describes the 3 most important and the 3 least important items that were rated by respondents as possible results of their teaching mobility experience. The most important results reported by academics are the expansion of their professional network (71,2% rated this as a direct result of their mobility), getting to know the culture, the educational system and the operation of higher education institutions in a foreign country (65,6% stated that it was a direct result of their mobility), and getting to know the work-culture of another organisation (64,3% stated that it was a direct result of their mobility). On the other hand, it seems that teaching mobility rarely contributes to introducing new joint degree programmes (79,1% reported that this hasn't happened), nor new courses/modules (65,8% reported that this hasn't happened). Overall, respondents rated items regarding professional development higher than those items that are dealing with other possible results. How these individual results translate to organisational results could be the question for another research project. The full distribution of the items regarding possible results is presented in the appendix.

5.9 MEASURED PERSONALITY AND ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS

Finally, the last section of the survey dealt with personality and organizational factors. These questions were presented to all respondents (for those who have already participated in teaching

mobility and for those as well, who haven't participated in the programme yet). Following the general idea of the Erasmus Impact Reports, we also included measurements of personal factors, that could be related to the indicators used in the cited source. This was not the explicit aim of our project, therefore we couldn't afford to buy licences to those kinds of measurement tools that are used in the Erasmus Impact Study, but we could use general scales which validity and reliability were proved by previous studies and could act as a proxy to those personality factors. The Erasmus Impact Study used 6 memo© factors: curiosity, serenity, confidence, tolerance for ambiguity, decisiveness, vigour. In relation to these factors, we chose to integrate three measures:

- tolerance for ambiguity scale (*Herman et al, 2010*)
- work-engagement as measured in vigour, dedication and absorption using the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale 9 items version (*Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004*)
- general self-efficacy scale (*Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995*)

In the appendix, we report the full descriptive statistics of the scales (created by taking the mean of all their items). Here, we just refer to the general means of the items. Further, in the discussion section, we will explore different connections to these variables, and we examine these personality factors comparing different groups as well (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Means of the dimensions of work engagement and personality factor scales.

Regarding descriptive results, it is not necessary to go into details analysing these numbers. We can acknowledge that regarding work engagement scale, our sample presents a rather high average, where absorption and dedication plays a more important role than vigour. On the other hand, measured personality factors like self-efficacy and tolerance of ambiguity also came up quite high. These variables will be examined in relations of different target groups.

6 MAIN FINDINGS OF THE RESEARCH

This chapter will review the research conducted on teaching mobility programme, examining personal characteristics (gender, age, work experience and title), some personal attitudes (self-efficacy, work engagement, tolerance of ambiguity) and several organisational factors. As it will emerge later, discipline determines various specifics of an institution, therefore with the help of a multivariate examination, it was verified that both institutional support on internationalization, institutional strategy on internationalization, the degree of satisfaction with information flow and the level of expectation of mobility are related to discipline. Using these factors, institutions were divided into three groups by clustering methods, creating the following profiles (Figure 24):

1. Low – low level of organisational attitude toward international teaching mobility programmes: mobility is less expected, there is less information or dissemination of the programmes, internationalization is less supported and there is a low strategic focus on it
2. Mild – mobility is moderately expected in these institutions, but information flow is above average, plus there is a moderate focus on internationalization
3. High – teaching mobility is highly expected, information flow is satisfactory, and the organizational focus on internationalization is high.

Figure 24. Organisational openness toward teaching mobility programmes.

The different attitudes toward teaching mobility programmes vary within disciplines (though it is statistically not proven due to the low number of cases in some of the fields). By looking at figure 25, emersion of health and medical sciences among the ratios of highly opened institutions is conspicuous.

Figure 25. Disciplines and organisational openness toward teaching mobility (not significant at level 95%).

In the following analysis – besides personal factors–, both discipline and organisational profile will be used in order to describe some characteristics of teaching mobility programmes according to the sample. In the pages that follow, participation in Erasmus+ programme, different hindering factors regarding teaching mobility, motivational factors, satisfaction with teaching mobility programme, return intent and the experienced results and effects of participating will be examined. Some of the features of the programmes (such as the length of the programme or the type of cooperation between the institutions) will also be presented in particular analysis.

6.1 PARTICIPATION IN ERASMUS+ TEACHING MOBILITY PROGRAMME

Participating in Erasmus+ teaching mobility programmes is related to some personal characteristics. A test of independence on this data shows that there are significant associations: those who have participated in Erasmus+ programmes are more likely to have higher academic rank, more work experience and are from the older age groups. While 62,2% of lecturer, assistant or junior professor participated in Erasmus+ programme, this ratio is 85,9% among professors, with a clear tendency. This association recurs when analysing age groups, where 32,1% of respondents under 30 have participated in the programme comparing to 84,5% among the oldest age group. Respondents' work experience is also related to whether or not they took part in teaching mobility programme: the highest ratio occurs among the most experienced ones. However, gender and discipline are not related to participation. Apparently, seizing the opportunity of gathering teaching experience abroad with Erasmus+ is more favoured among non-starter professors, according to the sample (Figure 26).

Figure 26. The ratio of Erasmus+ participants in several socio-demographics categories (significant at level 95%).

Attitudes toward work, self-efficacy and the tolerance of ambiguity seem independent of taking part in teaching mobility programme.

Institutional factors, such as the size or type of higher education institute are not related to participation, however, there are significant associations with organisational support and strategic focus on internationalization or with the presence of mobility as expectation. Internationalization on both factors and expectation of mobility are reported higher by those, who participated in Erasmus+ teaching mobility programmes (Figure 27).

Figure 27. Means of attitude toward internationalization and information flow (significant at level 95%).

According to information flow within a higher education institution, formal or informal sources are not related to participation. About two-thirds of participants gather information from informal sources (60,7%), and the ratio is independent of whether the respondent attended to teaching mobility programme or not. On the other hand, the number of possible information sources and the satisfaction with information flow is significantly higher among those, who participated in Erasmus+.

These findings though are not surprising, as those faculty members who applied for the programme should be involved in greater intensity, and therefore have more information from several sources. Nonetheless, the average number of applied information channels are slightly low. The most popular forms of information sources are online ones, such as e-mails (79,7%) and webpages (61,3%). The informal suggestion is the third one (44%), while campaigns or leadership suggestions stay below 15%. As a conclusion, the organisational approach to teaching mobility programmes determines respondents' participation. Not surprisingly, institutions with high support for teaching mobility programmes tend to have participants in a significantly higher ratio. While the ratio of participants is 55,9% in low supportive institutions, this ratio is 70,2% among mild supportive organisations and 79,8% among high supportive institutions (Table 1).

Table 1. Participation in Erasmus+ related organisational profile (significant at level 95%).

Ratio	Not participated	Participated
Low	44,1%	55,9%
Mild	29,8%	70,2%

High	20,2%	79,8%
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In summary, respondents differ within the categories of participants and non-participants in academic rank, age and work experience, but they scored the same in personal attitudes. The organisational profile also relates to participation: institutions where strategic focus and support on internationalization is higher, and where they provide more information about teaching mobility programmes, have a higher ratio of Erasmus+ participants.

6.2 HINDERING FACTORS

Participating in Erasmus+ affects how respondents see hindering factors regarding teaching mobility, however, intercultural issues (such as variant education system, student expectations and research attitudes in the host country) and the lack of competence or motivation are at the same level in both groups. Nevertheless, dealing with lack of time, connections or benefits when talking about teaching mobility programmes tends to disappear among those, who have already tried themselves abroad (Figure 28).

Figure 28. Hindering factors and participation in Erasmus+ teaching mobility (*significant at level 95%).

Lack of connection and reputation or communication issues are related to sociodemographic factors, as well, while other hindering factors are independent of age, work experience, title or gender.

Figure 29. Sociodemographic variables and hindering factor: lack of connection and reputation or communication issues (significant at level 95%).

The association may be tracked back to participating in Erasmus + programmes, as these factors were connected to that question, as well. Sociodemographic factors (except for gender) are significantly related to participation in Erasmus+ teaching mobility programme, which then affects how respondents consider obstacles such as lack of connections, reputation or communication issues. With a higher position, longer work experience and older age respondents face fewer difficulties according to this factor (Figure 29).

As for personal attitudes (Table 2), there are several significant correlations with hindering factors. It is worth to highlight, that intercultural difficulties (such as variant education system, students' expectations or research culture of the host institutions) are only connected to personal attitudes, while sociodemographic or organisational factors are independent of it. Self-efficacy, dedication and absorption are all significantly associated with intercultural difficulties. The more positive attitude participants have, the fewer difficulties they face regarding different attitudes in the host country. With one exception, the rest of correlations are of the same kind: greater self-efficacy comes with lower consideration of lack of benefits. Dedication to work and absorption correlates to fewer difficulties with lack of connections, reputation or communication issues and higher scores of tolerance of ambiguity connects to fewer difficulties with lack of competence and motivation (which is the strongest association among correlations, though it is still reported as moderate).

Table 2. The connection between personal attitudes and hindering factors (*significant at level 95%).

Correlation coefficient	Lack of connections, reputation or communication issues	Lack of competence and motivation	Intercultural difficulties	No benefits
Self efficacy	-0,056	-0,021	-,098*	-,101*
Work engagement - vigor	-0,057	0,018	-0,056	-0,074
Work engagement - dedication	-,111*	-0,078	-,110*	-0,09
Work engagement - absorption	-,156*	-0,085	-,102*	-0,026
Tolerance of ambiguity	0,009	-,305*	-,110*	,122*

The only positive association is between tolerance of ambiguity and the factor of no benefits, meaning that greater tolerance comes with reporting greater difficulties with the lack of benefits of teaching mobility programmes.

Although there were no significant differences between disciplines and participation in Erasmus+, examining the connection between field and hindering factors resulted in several findings showing that institutional attitude differs in health - and medical sciences compared to other disciplines. A test was conducted to examine the differences in hindering factors according to disciplines, where lack of time and financial support shows a statistically significant difference. After comparing the results in pairs, respondents in the field of health- and medical sciences appeared to have fewer difficulties with lack of time and financial support (-0,48) comparing to every other field. Lecturers from agricultural and veterinary disciplines ended on the other side of the scale (0,35), facing significantly greater difficulties regarding time and financial issues.

Disciplinary dissimilarity may originate from different attitudes toward internationalization among institutions in particular fields. While respondents from health- and medical sciences report the highest scores about organisational support and strategic focus regarding internationalization, scores in other fields are significantly lower. There is also a significant difference between natural sciences comparing to social sciences or humanities and arts (Figure 30).

Figure 30. Disciplinary differences in attitude toward internationalization (significant at level 95%).

Respondents from health- and medical sciences are not only supported by organisational attitude, but formal information flow is also reported as the best among the disciplines. While 32,7% of interviewees from health- and medical sciences gathered information through formal channels, this ratio is only 11,9% in natural sciences. However, this relationship is not proven statistically due to the low number of cases.

Another characteristic of an organisation which can affect hindering factors is the presence of mobility as expectation. It is also related to discipline, showing that in the field of health- and medical sciences the expectation is the highest (4,08 from 5), while the lowest score appeared at natural science.

Further examination of institutional factors was conducted related to hindering factors. Organisational support on internationalization also affects how respondents consider some of the factors. Difference between institutes with low support comparing to high supporters is statistically proven with the following factors: lack of time and financial support, lack of competence and motivation and lack of benefits. While facing the difficulties of lack of time, support and benefits appear in organisations with low support, lack of motivation reflects the opposite tendency: those who teach in highly supportive institutions, facing less (or none) difficulties with the lack of competence or motivation (Figure 31).

Figure 31. Organisational support of internationalization related to hindering factors (*significant at 95% level)

Strategic focus on internationalization relates significantly to a lack of competence and motivation and lack of benefits. However, hindering factors regarding lack of time and financial support are not depended on the organisation’s strategic focus, neither are intercultural difficulties or lack of connections and reputation or communication issues. According to the results, respondents from institutions with a low strategic focus on internationalization appear to face more difficulties with the lack of benefits, but on the other hand, the degree of lack of competence and motivation is significantly lower among them (Figure 32).

Figure 32. The strategic focus of internationalization related to hindering factors (*significant at 95% level).

Regarding information flow (Figure 33), the significant relationship appeared again related to lack of time and support, to lack of competence and motivation, and to lack of benefits. Where respondents have no information about teaching mobility programmes, the lack of time, financial support and the lack of benefits are significantly higher, showing the importance of formal dissemination when someone participated in teaching mobility program. However,

organizing formal events after a colleague participated in a particular teaching mobility program raises the degree of concern about the lack of competence and motivation.

Figure 33. Information flow and hindering factors (significant at level 95%).

The presence of mobility as expectation is correlated to some of the hindering factors, showing a similar tendency to previous findings. Where mobility is highly expected, respondents face fewer difficulties about time and financial support or think less about the lack of benefits, but on the other hand, considering lack of competence and motivation is higher among those, who belongs to an organisation where the level of mobility as expectation is higher.

As a conclusion, both organisational attitudes, information flow and mobility as expectation seems to be affected by disciplines – as it is written at the beginning of this chapter –, which then affects the degree of particular hindering factors, especially causing fewer concerns about the lack of time, financial support and benefits, while raising the scores for lack of competence and motivation. Personal characteristics, on the other hand, are only connected to lack of connections, reputation or communication issues, while international issues are correlated to personal attitudes.

6.3 MOTIVATION

As for motivational factors, gender, age, title and personal attitudes are significantly related to some of the elements. Having the motivation of expectation and urge depends on gender, where women scored significantly higher than men, meaning that they rather apply for a teaching mobility programme because they feel the urge and organisational expectation to do so. This factor significantly correlates to work engagement (especially vigour and dedication), and also

to the tolerance of ambiguity, where higher scores come with greater motivation. Learning languages or new pedagogical methods connects with age. Younger respondents report higher learning motivation, and it also significantly differs within titles, probably due to the clear relationship between age and academic rank. The motivation of learning is also affected by the level of vigour in work. Furthermore, higher self-efficacy and tolerance of ambiguity leads to motivation of getting to know new cultures, while the motivation of research opportunity connects with self-efficacy and absorption in work (Table 3).

Table 3. Personal attitudes and motivational factors
 (* significant at level 95%).

Correlation coefficient	Learning (language, pedagogical methods)	Getting to know new places, cultures	Research opportunities	Expectation, urge
Self efficacy	,107	,123*	,213*	,040
Work engagement - vigor	,143*	,058	,083	,178*
Work engagement - dedication	,028	,094	,080	,162*
Work engagement - absorption	,024	,046	,175*	,078
Tolerance of ambiguity	-,093	,128*	,006	-,263*

Two of the motivational factors significantly differ within organisational profiles. Those respondents, who belong to high supportive organisations, report greater motivation for learning and also higher expectation or urge. At the same time, getting to know new cultures, or taking the research opportunity of host institutions are independent of organisational characteristics (Table 4).

Table 4. Organisational profile and motivational factors
 (* significant at level 95%, minus=below average).

Mean	Learning (language, pedagogical methods)*	Getting to know new places, cultures	Research opportunities	Expectation, urge*
Low	-0.07	0.02	0.00	-0.46
Mild	-0.22	0.10	0.02	-0.29

High	0.22	0.01	0.08	0.37
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Learning relates to disciplines, as well. Higher motivation appears in the field of health - and medical sciences followed closely by agriculture and veterinary. Lowest learning motivation emerges in natural sciences and humanities and arts. The motivational force of research opportunity also depends on discipline. Greatest motivation appears in natural sciences, agriculture and veterinary, and engineering, while respondents from the field of humanities and arts or social sciences show lower motivation in learning or research (Table 5).

*Table 5. Disciplines and motivational factors
(* significant at level 95%, minus=below average).*

Mean	Learning (language, pedagogical methods)*	Getting to know new places, cultures	Research opportunities*	Expectation, urge
humanities and arts	-0.35	-0.07	-0.19	0.00
natural sciences	-0.20	0.03	0.38	-0.41
engineering	0.07	-0.11	0.22	-0.02
social sciences	0.11	-0.02	-0.13	0.05
agriculture and veterinary	0.32	-0.36	0.22	-0.28
health- and medical sciences	0.35	0.32	-0.01	0.02

The joint effect of discipline and organisational profile does not emerge when examining motivational factors, which means these factors affect motivation separately.

Satisfaction with preliminary expectation significantly correlates to the motivation factor of getting to know new places, while expectation or urge is significantly higher among those, who went for a short-term (2-5 days) programme. Furthermore, the motivation of expectation and urge also differ within the type of mobility agreement, where respondents who participated in repeated mobility scores higher in this motivation factor.

To sum up, the motivation of learning is connected to age, title and vigour work as personal factors, and it is also affected by discipline and organisational support on mobility programmes. Getting to know new cultures only relates to vigour work engagement and

tolerance for ambiguity, while research opportunity is associated with both personal attitudes and disciplines. Self-efficacy and absorption lead to higher motivation of research opportunities, as well as being a lecturer in the field of natural sciences, engineering or agriculture and veterinary. Expectation and urge are higher among women, among those who scored higher in vigour and dedication on work, and among those who are more intolerant for ambiguity. It is also connected to the organisational profile, where high supportive institutions lead to a higher score for urge and expectation as a motivational factor. Urge and expectation is also higher among short-termed and repeated mobility, suggesting that younger participants rather have the internal motivation (such as learning, getting to know new places, seizing research opportunity), while older respondents, who have participated in teaching mobility programmes earlier tend to have external motivation which is expectation or urge.

6.4 MOBILITY INTENTION, SATISFACTION AND RETURN INTENT

Respondents' mobility intention are correlated with self-efficacy and each component of work engagement, while none of the sociodemographic factors affects it significantly. On the other hand, organizational factors are also related to mobility intention: in those institutions where mobility is highly supported, respondents' intention to participate in mobility programmes are significantly higher.

Motivation and hindering factors also connect to mobility intention, where learning and getting to know new places show the positive relationship (meaning that higher motivation on these components results in higher mobility intention) while hindering factors show negative association: the more concerns respondents have, the lower his mobility intention is (Table 6).

Table 6. Motivation and hindering factors related to mobility intention
(* significant at level 95%).

Correlation coefficient	Motivation 1 - Learning (language, pedagogical methods)	Motivation 2 - Getting to know new places, cultures	Hindering 1 - Lack of time and financial support	Hindering 3 - Lack of competence and motivation	Hindering 4 - Intercultural difficulties	Hindering 5 -No benefits
Mobility intention	,169*	,128*	-,192*	-,103*	-,099*	-,208*

Type of discipline also relates significantly to mobility intention, where respondents from regional studies have higher mobility intention.

There is a significant and strong correlation between the satisfaction with mobility programme and return intent: higher the satisfaction, greater the return intent is. While personal attitudes correlate to both the degree of satisfaction with mobility programmes and of return intent, sociodemographic attributes are independent of them (Table 7).

Table 7. Personal attitudes related to satisfaction and return intent
(* significant at level 95%).

Correlation coefficient	Self-efficacy	Work engagement - vigour	Work engagement - dedication	Work engagement - absorption	Tolerance of ambiguity
Mobility - satisfaction	,267*	,282*	,285*	,231*	-0,006
Mobility - return intent	,203*	,218*	,210*	,156*	-0,014

Except for tolerance of ambiguity, both self-efficacy and elements of work engagement (vigour, dedication and absorption) are in a positive association, meaning that more positive attitude comes with higher satisfaction with mobility programme, and higher return intent, as well.

While these findings show correlations, a significant model of regression was also conducted to predict overall satisfaction. Useful feedback from students, self-efficacy and hindering factor of no benefits explains 22% of satisfaction, where feedback and self-efficacy contribute positively and the lack of benefits⁷ affects satisfaction negatively (Figure 34).

Figure 34. The predictive model of overall satisfaction

⁷ Negative scale for hindering factors means less concern about the particular factor, therefore negative affect means that less concern will result in higher satisfaction.

(significant at level 95%).

Overall satisfaction with mobility programme and return intent are not related to disciplines but are related to the organisational profile. Those respondents who belong to organisations that support teaching mobility are more satisfied with the programme, and they report higher intention to return to an upcoming mobility programme. The strongest connection is between the satisfaction of information at the institution, but all institutional factors are significantly correlated to both return intent and satisfaction with mobility programme (Figure 35).

Figure 35. Organisational support for teaching mobility programme related to return intent and satisfaction with mobility programme (significant at level 95%).

The interactional association between disciplines and organisational profiles disappear when examining return intent, for it is independent of disciplines and only affected by organisational profile. However, satisfaction with teaching mobility programme repeats the interaction, meaning that discipline's determination on organisational profile leads to different scores on satisfaction with mobility programme.

Length of programme and the type of cooperation is not connected to the satisfaction or return intent, but the degree of satisfaction with main expectations is strongly correlated to return intent and the overall satisfaction with the programme. Examining motivation factors, each of them shows a weak positive correlation with return intent and satisfaction, meaning that more motivated participants are more satisfied and has a higher intent to return.

An explanatory model shows a significant positive connection between return intent and learning motivation, while the lack of benefits, time and financial support negatively affects it⁸, explaining 10,4% of return intent ($R^2 = 0,104$). Therefore, return intent can be enhanced by greater learning motivation and fewer concerns about benefits, time and financial support (Figure 36).

Figure 36. The predictive model of return intent (significant at level 95%).

Several elements of teaching mobility were examined relating satisfaction (Figure 37), which scores show significant differences. Respondents are most satisfied with the help from the host institution (4,36 from 5-point scale), the time-frame (4,26) and with the required teaching load (4,23). Least satisfaction is seen by the amount of financial support (3,9) and administrative process (3,89).

⁸ Negative scale for hindering factors means less concern about the particular factor, therefore negative affect means that less concern will result in higher return intent.

Figure 37. Level of satisfaction with different parts of the programme (significant at level 95%).

When examining motivation and various parts of teaching mobility programmes, there is only a few weak correlations among the motivation of getting to know new places, research opportunities and expectation or urge. Availability of information is correlated to both of them, as well as satisfaction with the schedule of payment, or the help from the host institution. Each correlation is positive, meaning that higher motivation comes with significantly higher satisfaction.

Both for satisfaction and return intent an examination was conducted whether the type of discipline – such as foreign language, regional studies or nationally embedded – is related to them, but these factors seem independent.

In summary, overall satisfaction with teaching mobility programme and return intent are both related to personal attitudes and organisational profile, but they are independent of sociodemographic factors and discipline. Participants are most satisfied with the help from the host country and with time-frame of the programme, while financial support and administration are the least satisfying. Motivational factors also correlate to some of the elements of teaching mobility programmes, showing that higher motivation comes with higher satisfaction.

6.5 RESULTS AND EFFECTS

Results of mobility programmes are divided into four groups, which are education (eg. better teaching competence, new pedagogical methods), research (eg. opportunity to present empirical results at a conference, joining to a research team), professional development (eg. networking, development of interpersonal competencies), and organization (eg. greater intense of student mobility and cooperation with host institute).

A few significant associations emerged between the experienced results of participating in teaching mobility programmes and sociodemographic factors, and these are probably due to previous findings of personal traits and motivation. Gender relates to professional development, where female respondents report more development than male respondents. Age relates to results of organizational factors, where younger participants report increased added value of teaching mobility programme, than older ones.

„Wonderful opportunity to get familiarized with foreign higher education systems, getting to know teachers and students from other countries and become aware of differences in teaching cultures.”

Examining personal attitudes and experienced results of teaching mobility programmes show several significant findings. Positive associations emerged with self-efficacy and work engagement, but tolerance of ambiguity led to negative association. Encountering educational results correlates to each kind of work engagement (vigour, dedication, absorption), meaning

„I have participated in a joint seminar for doctorate students, which was a very critical learning process for me to re-evaluate our graduate seminars at home.”

that higher intensity of work engagement along these factors results in reporting more effect on teaching mobility programmes regarding education. Same is seen when looking at the effects in research, professional development or organisation, which are correlated

to self-efficacy, as well. On the other hand, those who have less tolerance of ambiguity reported more educational effect of teaching mobility programme (Table 8).

Table 8. Personal attitudes and results of the mobility programme
(*significant at level 95%).

Correlation coefficient	Results (education)	Results (research)	Results (professional development)	Results (organization)
Self efficacy	0.096	.137*	.161**	.212**
Work engagement - vigor	.209**	.147**	.264**	.292**
Work engagement - dedication	.187**	.164**	.230**	.280**
Work engagement - absorption	.137*	.149**	.132*	.163**
Tolerance of ambiguity	-.117*	-0.088	-0.077	-0.081

According to the sample, discipline and results of mobility programmes are not related, but organisational support affects the degree of results participant experienced during their programme. Institutions with high support come with significantly greater intensity of results in each area.

Figure 38. Organisational support and results of teaching mobility programmes (significant at level 95%).

According to figure 38, from experienced results of the mobility programme, the highest is professional development among every type of institutions.

Motivation and satisfaction with different parts of the programme correlate positively with the results. Each factor of motivation correlates with professional development and organization results. Research opportunity has a moderate correlation with research effects of the programme, and a weak connection to the rest of the result types (education, professional development, organization). Higher motivation of expectation or urge

„We have met and had discussions with numerous professors from the host institution and established the prospects of cooperation between our universities. We have exchanged publications and participated in conferences.”

comes with reporting more results in every area.

Satisfaction with each part of the programme also shows positive correlations with each area of results, except for research, which correlates weakly with available information, help from the host institute and required teaching load. Every correlation is significant and positive (mostly weak and moderate), meaning that a higher level of satisfaction connects to more experience regarding education, research, professional development or organization.

Besides these findings, a model of regression was conducted in order to predict overall results based on feedback, previous experience, and motivation. These variables explain 41,8% of results, meaning that with more feedback from students, more previous experience, higher motivation in expectation or research opportunities will lead to more results of teaching mobility programmes (Figure 39).

Figure 39. The predictive model of results (significant at level 95%).

Results can be divided into four segments, such as education, professional development, research and organisational. These types of results may be predicted by different factors, which was examined by further regression models. Numbers show that there are some common factors that affect each kind of results, such as feedback from students, previous experience and the motivation of research opportunities – three of the predictive factors from the derived results variable emerged in each of the segmented prediction models, as well (Figure 40).

Figure 40. Predictive factors for each kind of results (significant at level 95%).

Results on the side of education can be predicted by the level of learning motivation and organizational expectation, while results connected to research are only affected by organizational strategy on internationalization (above the common factors). Organizational results are higher with higher concerns about lack of competence and motivation, higher expectation and higher self-efficacy. Professional development has the most significant connection, it is growing with each component of motivation plus with higher concerns about lack of competence. Each connection is significant and positive, meaning that higher predictive factors grow the level of results in each component.

To sum up, results experienced by participants depend on personal characteristics, such as gender and age, and also some personal attitudes (self-efficacy, work engagement and tolerance for ambiguity). Women reported more professional development than men, while organization results ended up higher among younger respondents. Higher scores on personal attitudes show more experience, except for tolerance of ambiguity which comes with a negative correlation. Organisational support on teaching programmes also affects results, higher support means considering more results. Level of motivation and satisfaction connects to results as well, in a positive way.

7 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In summary, respondents differ within the categories of participants and non-participants in academic rank, age and work experience:

- seizing the opportunity of gathering teaching experience abroad with Erasmus+ is more favoured among non-starter professors, according to the sample
- the organisational profile also determines participation: institutions where strategic focus and support on internationalization is higher, and where they provide more information about teaching mobility programmes, have a higher ratio of Erasmus+ participants.

According to hindering factors, both organisational attitudes, information flow and mobility as expectation seems to be affected by disciplines, which then affects the degree of particular hindering factors:

- fields where organisational support on mobility programmes are high result in fewer concerns about the lack of time, financial support and benefits while raising the scores for lack of competence and motivation.

Personal characteristics were only connected to lack of connections, reputation or communication issues from hindering factors:

- the association may be tracked back to participating in Erasmus + programmes: sociodemographic factors (except for gender) are significantly related to participation in Erasmus+ teaching mobility programme, which then affects how respondents consider lack of connections, reputation or communication issues. With higher position, longer work experience and older age respondents face fewer difficulties according to this factor
- international issues are correlated to personal attitudes, where higher scores correlate to fewer concerns of international issues.

Different elements of motivation depend on various factors, suggesting that younger participants rather have the internal motivation (such as learning, getting to know new places, seizing research opportunity), while older and more experienced respondents, who have participated in teaching mobility programmes earlier tend to have external motivation which is expectation or urge:

- learning is connected to age, title and vigour work as personal factors, and it is also affected by discipline and organisational support on mobility programmes: higher motivation appears in the field of health - and medical sciences
- getting to know new cultures only relates to vigour work engagement and tolerance for ambiguity
- self-efficacy and absorption leads to higher motivation of research opportunities, as well as being a lecturer in the field of natural sciences, engineering or agriculture and veterinary
- expectation and urge are higher among women, among those who scored higher in vigour and dedication on work, and among those who are more intolerant for ambiguity. It is also connected to the organisational profile, where high supportive institutions lead

to a higher score, and it is also higher among short-termed programmes and repeated mobility.

Mobility intention is connected to motivation and hindering factors and some of the personal attitudes and organizational factors:

- highly supportive organization shows a higher intention
- mobility intention is higher among regional studies compared to foreign language or nationally embedded disciplines
- higher motivation results in higher mobility intention while hindering factors reduce the level of mobility intention
- higher self-efficacy and work engagement comes with higher mobility intention.

Overall satisfaction with teaching mobility programme and return intent are both related to personal attitudes and organisational profile, but they are independent of sociodemographic factors and discipline.

- participants are most satisfied with the help from the host country and with time-frame of the programme, while financial support and administration are the least satisfying
- motivational factors also correlate to some of the elements of teaching mobility programmes, showing that higher motivation comes with higher satisfaction
- return intent can be enhanced by greater learning motivation and fewer concerns about benefits, time and financial support, according to a predictive model
- overall satisfaction is affected by the amount of feedback from students, self-efficacy and lack of benefits.

Results experienced by participants depend on personal characteristics, such as gender and age, and also some personal attitudes (self-efficacy, work engagement and tolerance for ambiguity):

- women reported more professional development than men
- organization results ended up higher among younger respondents
- higher scores on personal attitudes show more experience, except for tolerance of ambiguity which comes with a negative correlation
- organisational support on teaching programmes also affects results, higher support means considering more results
- level of motivation and satisfaction connects to results as well, on a positive way
- according to a predictive model, higher motivation in expectation or research opportunities will lead to a greater amount of results of teaching mobility programmes.

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9 APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1. EXAMPLE OF A CUSTOMER JOURNEY MAP (FOR THE USER PERSONA: DR KRISTIANSOON)

[Link to larger version](#)

APPENDIX 2. PROTOCOL FOR PRELIMINARY INTERVIEWS

The aim of the semi-structured interviews is to explore the views of different stakeholders regarding experiences and possible impacts of teaching staff mobility at the individual and institutional level.

Results will be interpreted on different levels in a multi-stakeholder contingency approach:

- impact on the student level, on students and on teaching and learning
- impact on the teacher who participated in teaching staff mobility (pedagogical practice, attitudes, networking etc.)
- impact on the course / educational programme / work on the department
- impact on administration (direct organization and administration of teaching staff mobility)
- impact on a strategic level (internationalization)

Stakeholders:

- teachers who participated in teaching staff mobility programme;
- teachers who did not participate in teaching staff mobility programme but they have the aspiration to do so;
- students (who are taught by teachers who have participated in teaching staff mobility);
- administrative staff (responsible for the organization and administration of teaching staff mobility);
- leaders and managers (of teachers who have participated in teaching staff mobility; managers responsible for internationalisation);

Approximate length of interview: 20-40 minutes

Interviews can be conducted in any language, which is convenient for the interviewer and participant. For the analysis of the interviews, we would recommend recording the sessions either as a voice recording or provide written notes regarding the main points. **In case the interview is conducted in any other language than English, it is important to provide a detailed English summary.**

Questions:

The format of the interview is a semi-structured interview. The following questions are suggestions for a structure and process but as the interview proceeds, the interviewer can deviate from the suggested questions regarding the context. Either follow-up an interesting aspect more deeply or leave out unnecessary items.

1. Questions for all participants – except students! See point 4.

- Please briefly introduce yourself! (country of origin, studies, work/role, affiliation)
- Please describe in general your experiences regarding international mobility programmes!

- In your view, how popular are international mobility programmes among teachers, educators at your University/Department?
- What do you think might discourage/encourage teaching staff to participate in the Erasmus+ teaching staff mobility programme?
- What benefits does Erasmus teaching mobility bring to the University? How does teaching staff mobility contribute to international (or other) strategies at your University/Faculty/Department?
- What are some of the main challenges that your institution needs to address as far as teaching staff mobility is concerned?
- Please share with us one or more initiative or activity relating to teaching staff mobility at your institution that you consider meaningful.

2. Questions for teachers who participated in teaching staff mobility programme

- What was your main motivation for participating in the teaching staff mobility programme?
- Where/at which university did you teach in the teaching staff mobility programme? How long had this teaching period been?
- What were your preferences (country, the length of your visit etc.) for the participation in the teaching staff mobility programme?
- What are the possible effects and impacts of your mobility that you can perceive?
(If the participant doesn't mention, ask specifically these areas:
 - *your personal development?*
 - *your professional career?*
 - *your collaboration skills?*
- What competencies were you encouraged to develop at your host institution as part of your mobility experience?
- What challenges did you face before, during and after your visit?
(If the participant doesn't mention, please ask specifically about these areas:
 - *regarding contacting the host institution and organizing your visit*
 - *regarding professional issues of teaching (e.g. content)*
 - *regarding the administrative tasks of the mobility*
 - *everyday life, working condition and getting around the host institution and city, travel and accommodation)*
- In your view, had your visit have any impacts on the host institution? What impacts?
- How did you disseminate the outcomes of your visit?
- What could be the possible effects of your teaching mobility programme for your Department/University?

3. Questions for teachers did not participate in teaching mobility programme

- Do you think teaching staff mobility could contribute to your personal/professional development? How? To what extent?
- What are the main personal obstacles for you to participate in international teaching mobility programmes?

- What are the main professional obstacles for you to participate in international teaching mobility programmes?

4. Questions for administrative staff

- What are the most common challenges faced by teachers during their visit?
- What are the main (personal/professional) obstacles to teaching staff mobility?
- In your view, are there any administrative/management barriers at your university that led to teachers not applying for the teaching staff mobility programme?
- How might the University take better advantage of the Erasmus teaching mobility programme?
- Are there any current platforms for disseminating the results of teachers' mobility experience? If yes, please mention some of the practices
- In your opinion, how does teacher mobility programmes contribute to innovation at your institution?
- In what ways teachers' mobility experience add to the internationalization agenda at your institution?

5. Questions for students who are taught by teacher(s) with mobility experience

/General questions don't apply for students!/

- Please briefly introduce yourself! (country of origin, studies, mobility experience etc.)
- What outcomes do you think are resulted from your teacher's mobility experience? (personal/professional)
- What do you think, how could students benefit from their teachers participating in teaching staff mobility programmes?
- Do you consider international teaching mobility an important element of the teaching profession? Why do you think so?
- Have you ever participated in any mobility (short-term) programme during your studies? If yes, had you been inspired by any of your teachers for mobility?

APPENDIX 3. PROTOCOL FOR POST-SURVEY INTERVIEWS

The aim of the interviews is to get a better understanding of the results of the survey on teaching mobility. The questions are explicitly aimed at interesting or puzzling connections discovered in the data.

The format of the interview is a semi-structured interview. The following questions are suggestions for a structure and process but as the interview proceeds, the interviewer can deviate from the suggested questions regarding the context. Either follow-up an interesting aspect more deeply or leave out unnecessary items.

Approximate length of interviews: 20-40 minutes

Interviews can be conducted in any language, which is convenient for the interviewer and participant. For the analysis of the interviews, we would recommend recording the sessions either as a voice recording or provide written notes regarding the main points. **In case the interview is conducted in any other language than English, it is important to provide a detailed English summary.**

Possible participants:

- academic staff members who have already participated in teaching mobility
- professionals dealing with internationalisation in the higher education institution (HEI) (eg. administrative staff at international offices, vice-deans/vice-rectors for internationalisation etc.)

Questions:

1) Introduction

- Please briefly introduce yourself! (country of origin, studies, work/role, affiliation, relation to teaching mobility)

2) Organisational support

- Would you consider teaching mobility as an important opportunity for you and for your HEI?
 - (If yes): What makes teaching mobility important at your HEI?
 - (If no): Why?
- In what ways your HEI can support teaching mobility?
 - What further formal/informal methods can you identify?
 - How prevalent are these forms in your HEI?
- In your opinion, what could enhance the importance of teaching mobility at your HEI?
 - (If manager): How could you persuade/motivate your employees to go on teaching mobility?
 - (If not manager): How could you persuade your manager that teaching mobility is a worthwhile investment?

3) Impact and quality

- What would be the quality criteria from your point of view of successful teaching mobility?
 - as a teacher participating in the teaching mobility
 - as a teacher receiving a colleague for teaching mobility
 - as a manager responsible for internationalisation
- How could the quality of teaching mobilities be enhanced?
- It is often stated that teaching mobility comes with a great administrative burden – what would you suggest to decrease this workload or to rationalize it?
- Results of teaching mobility (eg. learning, connections) are often connected to the individual – do you have any suggestions or examples on how to encourage embedding these results and experiences to the operation of your HEI?
 - Could you mention a specific example when something that you have learnt on teaching mobility was later used at your HEI thanks to your experiences?

4) Pedagogical aspects

- What teaching methods worked for you when you were on teaching mobility?
 - What are the specific challenges of teaching and learning when on teaching mobility from your point of view?
- What methods do you use to get useful feedback from students regarding your teaching (at home / on teaching mobility)

APPENDIX 4. TEACH WITH ERASMUS+ QUESTIONNAIRE

- [Survey \(pdf\) – in English](#)
- [Survey \(pdf\) – in Hungarian](#)

APPENDIX 5. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE SAMPLE

Table 9. Respondents by country.

Country	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
Albania	1	0,14%
US Virgin Islands	1	0,14%
Austria	5	0,68%
Belgium	5	0,68%
Bulgaria	22	3,01%
Czech Republic	11	1,51%
Denmark	1	0,14%
South Georgia and South Sandwich Islands	1	0,14%
United Kingdom	5	0,68%
Estonia	2	0,27%
Finland	2	0,27%
France	15	2,05%
Greece	4	0,55%
Netherlands	1	0,14%
Croatia	70	9,59%
Iraq	1	0,14%
Ireland	3	0,41%
Iceland	1	0,14%
Colombia	1	0,14%
Poland	18	2,47%
Latvia	6	0,82%
Lithuania	27	3,70%
Hungary	159	21,78%
Germany	22	3,01%
Norway	29	3,97%
Italy	64	8,77%
Russia	2	0,27%
Portugal	14	1,92%
Romania	25	3,42%
Spain	44	6,03%
Switzerland	11	1,51%
Sweden	41	5,62%
Serbia	9	1,23%
Slovakia	96	13,15%
Slovenia	5	0,68%
Somalia	1	0,14%
Turkey	5	0,68%
Total	730	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	<i>15</i>	-

Table 10. Respondents by the operator of HEIs.

Operator of HEIs	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
State/public	692	94,10%
Non-state/private	43	5,90%
Total	735	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	10	-

Table 11. Respondents by type of HEIs.

Type of HEI	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
1. an institution with a focused (max 2-3 disciplines) educational programme (eg. University of Veterinary, University of Physical Education etc.)	60	8,29%
2. a vocational- or technical-oriented institution with a broader educational programme (at least 3-4 disciplines)	64	8,84%
3. a general institution with a broader educational programme (more than 4 disciplines) which primarily focuses on education	177	24,45%
4. a large and comprehensive institution with a strong research focus and intensive doctoral education	407	56,22%
Other	16	2,21%
Total	724	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	21	-

Table 12. Respondents by the size of HEIs.

Size of HEI	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
less than 500 students	17	2,40%
500-2.500 students	115	16,20%
2.500-10.000 students	197	27,80%
more than 10.000 students	380	53,60%
Total	709	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	36	-

Table 13. Respondents by disciplinary area.

Disciplinary area	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
natural sciences	66	8,92%
engineering	135	18,24%
health- and medical sciences	55	7,43%
agriculture and veterinary	11	1,49%
social sciences	258	34,86%
humanities and arts	162	21,89%
Other	53	7,16%
Total	740	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	5	-

Table 14. Type of discipline reported by respondents (multiple choice).

Type of discipline (multiple choice)	Number of respondents who selected the option	% of valid respondents who selected the option
1. My discipline focuses on a foreign language and/or culture.	134	18,10%
2. My discipline has some foreign regional focus (eg. international relations, geography)	153	20,70%
3. My discipline is highly embedded in a national context (eg. education, law)	160	21,60%
4. None of the above statements is true regarding my discipline.	343	46,40%

Table 15. Academic rank of respondents.

Academic rank	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
1. lecturer / assistant professor / junior professor	227	30,97%
2. senior lecturer / associate professor / hochschuldozent	206	28,10%
3. reader or associate professor / full professor / professor (without chair)	170	23,19%
4. professor / distinguished professor / professor (with chair)	87	11,87%
5. Other	43	5,87%
Total	733	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	12	-

Table 16. The number of years respondents' are working at their current HEI.

Number of years at the current HEI	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
less than 5 years	148	20,03%
6-10 years	141	19,08%
11-15 years	164	22,19%
16-20 years	121	16,37%
21-25 years	73	9,88%
more than 25 years	92	12,45%
Total	739	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	6	-

Table 17. International experiences of respondents.

International experience	I don't have such an experience		I have participated in this kind of programme once		I have participated in this kind of programme twice		I have participated in this kind of programme three times		I have participated in this kind of programme four times		I have participated in this kind of programme for five times or more		Total		Missing data
	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	
Longer mobility for the purpose of study	416	65,80%	100	15,80%	29	4,60%	28	4,40%	16	2,50%	43	6,80%	632	100%	113
Teaching mobility	174	24,65%	144	20,40%	106	15,01%	85	12,04%	55	7,79%	142	20,11%	706	100%	39
Mobility for research purposes	290	45,31%	134	20,90%	70	10,94%	56	8,80%	29	4,53%	61	9,50%	640	100%	105
Intensive programme or a national cooperation project	346	55,81%	96	15,48%	68	11,00%	34	5,48%	29	4,70%	47	7,58%	620	100%	125
Participation/speaking at an international conference/works hop	96	14,37%	51	7,60%	71	10,63%	52	7,80%	49	7,30%	349	52,25%	668	100%	77

Table 18. Distribution of respondents by gender.

Gender	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
female	424	57,84%
male	309	42,16%
Total	733	100%
Missing data	12	-

Table 19. Distribution of respondents by age.

Age	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
younger than 30	33	4,50%
31-40 years old	204	27,80%
41-50 years old	249	33,90%
51-60 years old	181	24,70%
older than 60	67	9,10%
Total	734	100%
Missing data	11	-

Table 20. Distribution of respondents by their participation in Erasmus+ Teaching Mobility.

Participation in E+ teaching mobility	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
no	204	31,00%
yes	455	69,00%
Total	659	100%
Missing data	86	-

Table 21. Distribution of respondents regarding the statements of organisational support and strategic approach to internationalisation.

Organisational support of internationalisation	1	2	3	4	5
In my organisation colleagues are being encouraged to participate in teaching mobility. (N=681)	4,26%	13,22%	22,61%	25,40%	34,51%
In my organisation, colleagues are being supported to participate in teaching mobility. (N=676)	5,03%	11,83%	19,23%	29,14%	34,76%

In my organisation teaching mobility is considered as an attractive opportunity. (N=667)	5,40%	15,29%	23,39%	25,94%	29,99%
In my organisation, we consider teaching mobility as an important, profitable investment. (N=655)	7,79%	16,49%	21,83%	26,41%	27,48%
If I would be on teaching mobility and therefore would have to miss my classes, then my organisation would provide a substitution for my classes (N=628)	27,55%	12,26%	17,68%	16,40%	26,11%
In my organisation, there is an opportunity to organise my classes in a way that I could go on teaching mobility. (N=649)	8,63%	9,24%	16,80%	24,19%	41,14%
Regarding my professional career development, teaching mobility is considered as a recognized activity in my organisation (N=653)	10,87%	13,02%	21,13%	24,66%	30,32%
Strategic approach to internationalisation	1	2	3	4	5
Internationalisation is an integral part of the institutional strategy. (N=680)	2,06%	7,21%	14,71%	26,76%	49,26%
My organisation specifically supports the international mobility of academics and staff. (N=673)	3,86%	9,36%	18,72%	29,27%	38,78%
My organisation specifically supports the teaching mobility of academics. (N=672)	4,91%	11,16%	19,05%	27,53%	37,35%
My organisation searches for and attracts academics and staff that have an international orientation. (N=653)	8,12%	15,77%	21,44%	27,41%	27,26%
My organisation's approach to learning and teaching shows an international orientation. (N=661)	6,66%	13,62%	23,60%	29,50%	26,63%
My organisation's approach to research and development shows an international orientation. (N=657)	3,65%	9,89%	19,03%	33,79%	33,64%

Notes. Total N=745; the number of respondents indicated by the statements are indicating valid responses.

Table 22. Number of international programmes at the participants' institution.

International programmes	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
1. We don't have any foreign language programmes.	81	13,00%
2. We've just begun experimenting, we only have one-two programmes in a foreign language.	135	21,60%

3. We have one-two well-established programmes in a foreign language.	165	26,40%
4. We have three or more programmes in a foreign language.	243	38,90%
Total	624	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	<i>121</i>	-

Table 23. Ratio of international students at the participants' institution.

Ratio of international students	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
1. We don't have any international students.	9	1,40%
2. We only have a few international students.	149	23,70%
3. Less than 10% of our students are international.	261	41,40%
4. Approximately 11-25% of our students are international.	175	27,80%
5. Approximately 25-50% of our students are international.	32	5,10%
6. More than half of our students are international.	4	0,60%
Total	630	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	<i>115</i>	-

Table 24. Form of dissemination regarding mobility experiences as reported by participants.

Form of dissemination regarding mobility experiences	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
1. ... I usually do not know about it.	107	15,90%
2. ... I know about it by informal discussions.	409	60,70%
3. ... I know about it by formal events (eg. faculty meeting)	144	21,40%
Other	14	2,10%
Total	674	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	<i>71</i>	-

Table 25. Source of information regarding teaching mobility opportunities as reported by participants.

Source of information regarding teaching mobility opportunities (multiple choice)	Number of respondents who selected the option	% of valid respondents who selected the option
1. information available on the webpage of my organisation	419	61,30%
2. e-mails/ mailing lists	545	79,70%
3. marketing campaign (written form, eg. poster)	78	11,40%
4. marketing campaign (oral form, eg. info sessions)	96	14,00%
5. informal recommendations from my colleagues	304	44,40%
6. in the form of encouragement by the leadership	125	18,30%
7. in the form of direct expectations from the leadership	44	6,40%
8. teaching mobility is embedded in my professional development plan	76	11,20%
9. Other	29	4,20%

Table 26. Satisfaction with the method of information-sharing regarding teaching mobility.

Satisfaction with the method of information-sharing	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
1 - not at all	34	5,10%
2	59	8,80%
3	141	21,10%
4	195	29,20%
5 - absolutely	238	35,70%
Total	667	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	78	-

Table 27. Mobility perceived as an expectation by the respondents.

Mobility as expectation	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
1 - not at all	68	10,50%
2	98	15,10%
3	162	25,00%
4	162	25,00%
5 - absolutely	159	24,50%

Total	649	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	96	-

Table 28. Respondents' intention to go on teaching mobility in the following years.

Intention to go on a mobility	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
0 - not likely	26	3,90%
1	15	2,30%
2	20	3,00%
3	31	4,70%
4	14	2,10%
5	38	5,70%
6	28	4,20%
7	51	7,70%
8	88	13,30%
9	72	10,90%
10 - absolutely	279	42,10%
Total	662	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	83	-

Table 29. Hindering factors regarding participation in teaching mobility.

Hindering factors	1 - not significant issue		2		3		4		5 - very significant issue		Total		Missing data
	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents
It comes with great inconvenience to organise and execute it.	197	31,70%	101	16,20%	134	21,50%	113	18,20%	77	12,40%	622	100%	123
There are no opportunities in those languages that I speak.	462	74,40%	64	10,31%	50	8,05%	18	2,90%	27	4,35%	621	100%	124
I'm not confident enough in my foreign language skills.	419	66,60%	93	14,80%	61	9,70%	27	4,30%	29	4,60%	629	100%	116
I'm not confident enough in my pedagogical competences.	448	71,22%	99	15,74%	50	7,95%	23	3,66%	9	1,43%	629	100%	116
I don't want to leave my family even for a short period of time.	326	52,16%	94	15,00%	100	16,00%	56	9,00%	49	7,80%	625	100%	120
I have no time to participate in such activities.	232	36,48%	111	17,45%	137	21,54%	92	14,47%	64	10,06%	636	100%	109
I can't finance my mobility in advance.	281	37,72%	83	11,14%	104	13,96%	73	9,80%	89	11,95%	630	100%	115
I fear that the budget available in the programme wouldn't be enough.	203	32,85%	117	18,93%	123	19,90%	102	16,50%	73	11,81%	618	100%	127
It is hard for me to plan this opportunity ahead.	231	36,67%	138	21,90%	131	20,79%	85	13,49%	45	7,14%	630	100%	115
I can't solve my substitution at my workplace.	221	35,36%	131	20,96%	108	17,28%	89	14,24%	76	12,16%	625	100%	120
I don't have enough information regarding the opportunity.	338	53,40%	119	18,80%	77	12,16%	57	9,00%	42	6,64%	633	100%	112
I don't have adequate contacts.	292	46,28%	113	17,91%	103	16,32%	59	9,35%	64	10,14%	631	100%	114
It would be hard for me to organize the required number of lessons.	302	48,55%	143	22,99%	104	16,72%	45	7,23%	28	4,50%	622	100%	123
I'm not a well-known academic in my field yet for host institutions to accept me.	293	48,11%	115	18,88%	97	15,93%	59	9,69%	45	7,39%	609	100%	136
It is hard to communicate with the host institution.	268	45,35%	132	22,34%	114	19,29%	56	9,48%	21	3,55%	591	100%	154
I find administrative tasks regarding teaching mobility quite complicated.	192	31,63%	148	24,38%	128	21,09%	74	12,19%	65	10,71%	607	100%	138
In my organisation, teaching mobility is not a priority.	226	36,87%	118	19,25%	116	18,92%	87	14,19%	66	10,77%	613	100%	132
Teaching mobility doesn't play an important role in my professional development.	249	40,69%	117	19,12%	107	17,48%	75	12,25%	64	10,46%	612	100%	133
Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different national/educational systems.	295	48,84%	154	25,50%	92	15,23%	45	7,45%	18	2,98%	604	100%	141
Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different needs and expectations of students.	296	48,93%	158	26,12%	92	15,21%	42	6,94%	17	2,81%	605	100%	140
Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different research / disciplinary culture of the host institution.	290	49,24%	141	23,94%	105	17,83%	37	6,28%	16	2,72%	589	100%	156
I wouldn't be able to take advantage of the experience at my home institution.	333	55,97%	118	19,83%	77	12,94%	42	7,06%	25	4,20%	595	100%	150
I don't have any motivation to participate.	431	69,63%	70	11,31%	68	10,99%	22	3,55%	28	4,52%	619	100%	126
I prefer someone else to seize the opportunity	369	62,76%	72	12,24%	74	12,59%	37	6,29%	36	6,12%	588	100%	157
Other	8	26,67%	1	3,33%	7	23,33%	0	0,00%	14	46,67%	30	100%	715

Table 30. Distribution of the sample regarding their participation in Erasmus+ teaching mobility programme.

Participation in E+ teaching mobility	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
haven't participated	204	31,00%
already participated	455	69,00%
Total	659	100%
Missing data	86	-

Table 31. Year, when the participants embarked on their teaching mobility.

Year of the teaching mobility	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
2009	13	2,97%
2010	5	1,14%
2011	5	1,14%
2012	8	1,83%
2013	9	2,06%
2014	15	3,43%
2015	10	2,29%
2016	28	6,41%
2017	56	12,81%
2018	120	27,46%
2019	168	38,44%
Total	437	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	308	-

Table 32. Target countries for teaching mobility reported in our sample.

Target country of respondents for the teaching mobility	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
Spain	41	9,51%
Poland	36	8,35%
France	27	6,26%
Germany	27	6,26%
Portugal	27	6,26%
Czech Republic	22	5,10%
Italy	19	4,41%
Romania	18	4,18%
United Kingdom	17	3,94%
Austria	15	3,48%
Hungary	12	2,78%
Turkey	12	2,78%
Finland	11	2,55%
Lithuania	11	2,55%
Netherlands	10	2,32%
Belgium	9	2,09%
Croatia	8	1,86%

Latvia	8	1,86%
Serbia	8	1,86%
Cyprus	7	1,62%
Greece	7	1,62%
Bulgaria	6	1,39%
Slovenia	5	1,16%
Denmark	4	0,93%
South Korea	4	0,93%
United States	4	0,93%
Egypt	4	0,93%
Iceland	4	0,93%
Morocco	4	0,93%
Slovakia	4	0,93%
Estonia	3	0,70%
Israel	3	0,70%
Jordan	3	0,70%
Norway	3	0,70%
Russia	3	0,70%
Ukraine	3	0,70%
Argentina	2	0,46%
Bosnia and Herzegovina	2	0,46%
Thailand	2	0,46%
Vietnam	2	0,46%
Albania	1	0,23%
Holy See	1	0,23%
Bangladesh	1	0,23%
Guatemala	1	0,23%
India	1	0,23%
Indonesia	1	0,23%
Japan	1	0,23%
Canada	1	0,23%
Kazakhstan	1	0,23%
China	1	0,23%
Macedonia	1	0,23%
Malta	1	0,23%
Moldova	1	0,23%
Sweden	1	0,23%
Total	431	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	<i>314</i>	-

Table 33. Language spoken by respondents during their teaching mobility.

Language used during teaching mobility	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
English	332	74,77%
Bulgarian	1	0,23%
Czech	2	0,45%
Finnish	1	0,23%
French	17	3,83%
Greek	1	0,23%
Dutch	1	0,23%
Croatian	4	0,90%
Polish	5	1,13%
Hungarian	11	2,48%
German	18	4,05%
Norwegian	2	0,45%
Italian	5	1,13%
Russian	5	1,13%
Portuguese	1	0,23%
Romanian	3	0,68%
Spanish	14	3,15%
Slovak	12	2,70%
Turkish	1	0,23%
Ukrainian	1	0,23%
Other	7	1,58%
Total	444	100%
Missing data	301	-

Table 34. Preliminary conditions regarding the agreement between the host and home institutions.

Context of the mobility	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents
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1. It was a new mobility, we didn't have any prior agreement with the host institution.	64	14,75%
2. We had a mobility agreement between our institutions, but we didn't have a teaching mobility exchange before.	134	30,88%
3. We had a mobility agreement between our institutions and other colleagues have already been on teaching mobility at this institution.	132	30,41%
4. We had a mobility agreement between our institutions and I was on previous teaching mobility at this institution.	99	22,81%
Other	5	1,15%
Total	434	100%
<i>Missing data</i>	<i>311</i>	-

Table 35. Motivational factors regarding participation in teaching mobility.

Motivation factors	1 - not important		2		3		4		5 - very important		Total		Missing data Number of respondents
	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	
A previous teaching mobility experience	103	24,40%	19	4,50%	50	11,80%	73	17,30%	177	41,90%	422	100%	323
Recommendation from a colleague	144	34,40%	47	11,20%	62	14,80%	70	16,70%	96	22,90%	419	100%	326
Encouragement from the leadership	162	38,90%	59	14,20%	71	17,10%	53	12,70%	71	17,10%	416	100%	329
Expectation from my organisation	161	38,40%	72	17,20%	79	18,90%	53	12,60%	54	12,90%	419	100%	326
I love to travel	33	7,70%	38	8,90%	69	22,40%	96	22,40%	192	44,90%	428	100%	317
I wanted to learn about the culture of the host country	35	8,20%	28	6,60%	61	14,30%	92	21,60%	210	49,30%	426	100%	319
I wanted to learn about the higher education system of the host country	15	3,50%	25	5,80%	47	10,80%	126	29,00%	221	50,90%	434	100%	311
I wanted to learn about the educational practices at the host institution	7	1,60%	10	2,30%	51	11,70%	117	26,90%	250	57,50%	435	100%	310
I wanted to learn about the research projects of the host institution	10	2,30%	19	4,40%	51	11,90%	120	28,10%	227	53,20%	427	100%	318
Possible research opportunities	20	4,60%	18	4,20%	65	15,10%	115	26,70%	213	49,40%	431	100%	314
Possible opportunities for joint-projects	10	2,30%	18	4,20%	50	11,60%	102	23,60%	252	58,30%	432	100%	313
To improve my foreign language skills	83	19,50%	35	8,20%	63	14,80%	91	21,40%	153	36,00%	425	100%	320
To improve my competencies in teaching in a foreign language	53	12,40%	18	4,20%	51	11,90%	117	27,30%	190	44,30%	429	100%	316
To improve my general pedagogical competencies	29	6,70%	26	6,00%	90	20,90%	101	23,50%	184	42,80%	430	100%	315
To try out myself in a foreign language environment	58	13,60%	23	5,40%	62	14,50%	96	22,50%	188	44,00%	427	100%	318
Other	9	33,30%	0	0,00%	2	7,40%	3	11,10%	13	48,10%	27	100%	718

Table 36. Satisfaction with different elements of the teaching mobility.

Satisfaction	1 - not satisfied		2		3		4		5 - very satisfied		Total		Missing data Number of respondents
	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	
Availability of information	2	0,50%	25	5,80%	71	16,50%	124	28,80%	209	48,50%	431	100%	314
Amount of financial support	12	2,80%	37	8,60%	96	22,20%	125	28,90%	162	37,50%	432	100%	313
Schedule of payment	14	3,30%	34	8,00%	63	14,80%	114	26,70%	202	47,30%	427	100%	318
Administrative process	14	3,20%	38	8,80%	91	21,10%	127	29,50%	161	37,40%	431	100%	314
Help from the home institution in organising the mobility	12	2,80%	23	5,40%	66	15,40%	90	21,00%	237	55,40%	428	100%	317
Help from the host institution in organizing the mobility	6	1,40%	13	3,00%	55	12,70%	103	23,80%	256	59,10%	433	100%	312
The required teaching load	2	0,50%	16	3,80%	76	17,90%	118	27,80%	213	50,10%	425	100%	320
The time-frame of the mobility	4	0,90%	19	4,40%	58	13,60%	127	29,70%	219	51,30%	427	100%	318

Table 37. Received feedback and their usefulness reported by the respondents regarding their activity during the teaching mobility.

	Feedback	0 – I haven't received feedback		1 - I have received feedback but it wasn't		2 – I have received useful feedback		Total		Missing data
		Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents
From the students of the host institution	regarding my teaching methods	193	45,31%	28	6,57%	205	48,12%	426	100%	319
	regarding the content of my lecture	121	28,40%	33	7,75%	269	63,59%	423	100%	322
	regarding how interesting my lecture was	108	25,35%	26	6,10%	288	68,25%	422	100%	323
	regarding the usefulness of my lecture	149	34,98%	29	6,81%	241	57,52%	419	100%	326
	regarding the importance of my research area	205	48,12%	42	9,86%	170	40,77%	417	100%	328
	regarding my language and communication skills	213	50,00%	33	7,75%	175	41,57%	421	100%	324
	Other (from students)	82	19,25%	6	1,41%	31	26,05%	119	100%	626
From the colleagues of the host institution	regarding my teaching methods	131	30,75%	17	3,99%	273	64,85%	421	100%	324
	regarding the content of my lecture	72	16,90%	23	5,40%	324	77,33%	419	100%	326
	regarding how interesting my lecture was	82	19,25%	21	4,93%	313	75,24%	416	100%	329
	regarding the usefulness of my lecture	99	23,24%	27	6,34%	296	70,14%	422	100%	323
	regarding the importance of my research area	139	32,63%	34	7,98%	244	58,51%	417	100%	328
	regarding my language and communication skills	180	42,25%	34	7,98%	203	48,68%	417	100%	328
	Other (from colleagues)	81	19,01%	6	1,41%	38	30,40%	125	100%	620

Table 38. Different results of teaching mobility reported by participants.

Results	0 – It hasn't happened or my mobility hasn't contributed to this		1 – My mobility contributed a little to this result		2 – This result is achieved thanks to my mobility		Total		Missing data
	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	Number of respondents	% of valid respondents	
Educational results									
I understand our international students better (not language-wise)	49	11,64%	153	36,34%	219	52,02%	421	100%	324
I can better adapt to the different needs and expectations of students	33	7,84%	155	36,82%	230	54,63%	418	100%	327
I have learnt new teaching methods	113	26,84%	155	36,82%	156	37,05%	424	100%	321
I have become more conscious regarding my approach to teaching	47	11,16%	152	36,10%	224	53,21%	423	100%	322
My pedagogical competences have improved	62	14,73%	163	38,72%	196	46,56%	421	100%	324
Students now have the opportunity to participate in joint professional practices and fieldwork with the host institution	139	33,02%	111	26,37%	137	32,54%	387	100%	358
We have developed new course contents and materials with the colleagues of the host institution	201	47,74%	109	25,89%	96	22,80%	406	100%	339
We have developed new courses with the colleagues of the host institution	228	54,16%	96	22,80%	81	19,24%	405	100%	340
Other (related to education)	13	3,09%	2	0,48%	11	2,61%	26	100%	719
Research results									
Opportunity to present my research results	55	13,06%	134	31,83%	229	54,39%	418	100%	327
Opportunity to get to know research projects at the host institution	55	13,06%	127	30,17%	240	57,01%	422	100%	323
Access to the infrastructure of the host institution (library, databases etc.)	125	29,69%	142	33,73%	152	36,10%	419	100%	326
Receive feedback on my topic	73	17,34%	149	35,39%	195	46,32%	417	100%	328
I was able to submit an article to an international scholarly journal	241	57,24%	75	17,81%	92	21,85%	408	100%	337
I was able to write a joint publication with the colleagues of the host institution	227	53,92%	99	23,52%	84	19,95%	410	100%	335
I was able to launch a joint research project with the host institution	221	52,49%	100	23,75%	86	20,43%	407	100%	338
I have invited a colleague from the host institution as a keynote speaker for our conference	155	36,82%	105	24,94%	150	35,63%	410	100%	335
I was invited to be a keynote speaker in a conference organized by the host institution	232	55,11%	64	15,20%	111	26,37%	407	100%	338
Other (related to research)	13	3,09%	1	0,24%	11	2,61%	25	100%	720
Professional development results									
My professional network has expanded	17	4,04%	106	25,18%	304	72,21%	427	100%	318
I was invited as a guest lecturer to the host institution	188	44,66%	75	17,81%	153	36,34%	416	100%	329
The content that I was teaching became a part of the regular curriculum of the host institution and I regularly teach that course there	247	58,67%	85	20,19%	70	16,63%	402	100%	343
My mobility experience had a positive impact on my career development	97	23,04%	160	38,00%	160	38,00%	417	100%	328
I've got to know the culture, educational system and the operation of higher education institutions of a foreign country	22	5,23%	124	29,45%	279	66,27%	425	100%	320
I've got to know the work-culture of another organisation	21	4,99%	131	31,12%	274	65,08%	426	100%	319
My stress-management skills have improved	127	30,17%	138	32,78%	142	33,73%	407	100%	338
I became more flexible	102	24,23%	144	34,20%	162	38,48%	408	100%	337
My interpersonal skills have improved	64	15,20%	148	35,15%	202	47,98%	414	100%	331
My language skills have improved	90	21,38%	146	34,68%	176	41,81%	412	100%	333
My cooperation skills have improved	65	15,44%	154	36,58%	203	48,22%	422	100%	323
My intercultural skills have improved	42	9,98%	161	38,24%	221	52,49%	424	100%	321
My professional overview has been expanded	28	6,65%	138	32,78%	256	60,81%	422	100%	323
I became more motivated, the mobility experience inspired me	34	8,08%	122	28,98%	261	62,00%	417	100%	328
Other (related to professional development)	8	1,90%	4	0,95%	9	2,14%	21	100%	724
Organisational results									
My institution became known at the host institution	43	10,21%	130	30,88%	240	57,01%	413	100%	332
We have introduced a new course / module in our institution thanks to my mobility experiences	267	63,42%	80	19,00%	59	14,01%	406	100%	339
We have introduced a new joint degree programme with the host institution	322	76,48%	44	10,45%	41	9,74%	407	100%	338
The international reputation of my home institution increased in the eyes of our students	100	23,75%	153	36,34%	147	34,92%	400	100%	345
My mobility contributed to the implementation of the internationalization strategy of our institution	81	19,24%	155	36,82%	168	39,90%	404	100%	341
Thanks to my mobility, the number of student mobilities between the two institutions has increased	138	32,78%	122	28,98%	120	28,50%	380	100%	365
My trust has grown regarding accepting ECTS from external institutions	131	31,12%	125	29,69%	119	28,27%	375	100%	370
Other (related to organisational results)	12	2,85%	6	1,43%	12	2,85%	30	100%	715

Table 39. Descriptives statistics regarding certain personality factors reported by respondents.

Personality factors	N	Min.	Max.	M 95% CI	SD
Work Engagement - Vigor	593	0,00	6,00	4,05 95% CI [3,93; 4,16]	1,26
Work Engagement - Dedication	608	0,33	6,00	4,86 95% CI [4,79; 4,99]	1,12
Work Engagement - Absorption	586	0,67	6,00	4,82 95% CI [4,74; 4,93]	1,06
Tolerance of Ambiguity	484	1,00	5,00	3,43 95% CI [3,39; 3,48]	0,49
Self-Efficacy	554	1,10	5,00	3,93 95% CI [3,91; 4,02]	0,59